

MODEL-DRIVEN PARAMETER RECONSTRUCTIONS FROM SMALL ANGLE X-RAY SCATTERING IMAGES

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Abstract

The diagnostic of plasma dynamical processes at solid densities and at the time and length scales involved in the formation of instabilities has become accessible in experiments by coherent X-ray scattering techniques through the advent of X-ray free-electron lasers. In this thesis, models for the density of structured targets under the influence of plasma expansion are studied. A general analytical derivation of the scattering signal of such targets is given and it is investigated what kind of statements regarding the expansion profile can be made based on data analyses that comprise various parametrical density models. To enable numerical investigations of experimental X-ray intensities with reduced parametrical density models, a framework has been designed in Python. The operability of the framework is demonstrated with data from experiments. Based on the results, statistically robust multi-model reconstructions of the plasma density that use the presented framework are envisioned.

Zusammenfassung

Die experimentelle Diagnostik der Dynamik von festkörperdichten Plasmen auf den für das Entstehen von Instabilitäten relevanten Längen- und Zeitskalen mit Methoden der kohärenten Röntgenstreuung ist durch die Einführung von Röntgen-Freie-Elektronen-Lasern möglich geworden. In dieser Arbeit werden Modelle für die Dichte eines regelmäßig strukturierten Targets unter dem Einfluss der Plasma-Expansion untersucht. Es wird eine allgemeine analytische Herleitung für das Streusignal solcher Targets gegeben und untersucht, welche Rückschlüsse auf das Expansionsprofil anhand von Datenanalyse mit verschiedenen parametrischen Dichtemodellen möglich sind. Zur numerischen Untersuchung von gemessenen Röntgen-Intensitäten im Experiment anhand reduzierter parametrischer Dichtemodelle wurde ein Framework in Python entwickelt. Die Funktionstüchtigkeit des Frameworks wird an experimentellen Daten gezeigt. Die Ergebnisse stellen statistisch robuste modellübergreifende Rekonstruktionen der Plasmadichte durch die Verwendung des vorgestellten Frameworks in Aussicht.

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1. MOTIVATION

Radiation therapy is a well-established method for treating malignant tumors which has advantages over surgical treatment or chemotherapy. Ion beams are especially well-suited as they deliver a better depth-dose profile [Wil46] than photon beams and thus allow for the precise application of a medically relevant dose while sparing the surrounding healthy tissue. For 50 years [GM66], the basic mechanisms of laser-driven ion acceleration (LDIA) have been studied. LDIA is especially attractive for application in medical facilities as it promises to be less costly and space-consuming than conventional accelerators [BK01] [Bul+02] [Mal+04] [Ma+06]. Enormous theoretical and experimental progress has been made [Sna+00] [Mak+00] [Gai+11] [Wag+16] up until now. However, the increase of the achievable energies to the medically relevant level of 200 MeV is still an active research area. The adoption as a medical technique furthermore requires precise control over the beam parameters and a stable high-quality ion beam. A typical acceleration scheme employs an ultra-high intensity (UHI, $\sim 10^{18} - 10^{21}$ W/cm²) short (30 – 150 fs) laser pulse that interacts with a μm -thick solid density foil target. A plasma is created and the displacement of several nano-Coulombs of charge creates accelerating electrostatic fields of the order of \sim TV/m. Recent theoretical works have delivered scaling laws for the maximum attainable ion energy depending on laser power [Klu+11]. Nevertheless, recent experiments at the Draco laser system have shown an upper limit to the applicability of these scaling laws [Sch+17]. Close cooperation of experiment, theory and simulation support strongly hint that the ideal scaling is impeded as non-linear processes in all regions of the target become more important as the laser power grows [Met+14] [Göd+17]. Simulations of electron dynamics on length scales of a few nanometers to tens of nanometers and time scales of femtoseconds show the growth of instabilities. In order to further increase maximum ion energy and establish precise control over the beam, experimental diagnostic methods take a key role in helping to understand the involved processes. Such diagnostic methods require a high spatial as well as temporal resolution at the same time which has only recently become achievable with the advent of X-ray free electron lasers (XFELs). These large-scale machines provide coherent X-ray pulses that are sufficiently short in time (2 – 100 fs) [al06] and have a sufficiently high number of photons (up to 10^{12}) per pulse to deliver a measurable signal with a single shot. Thus, X-ray scattering experiments can be devised that are able to resolve the small structures and time scales of the laser-ion-acceleration process [Klu+14] [Klu+16] [Klu+17b]. Scattering images obtained in such experiments result from all possible photon interactions of the X-ray probe-pulse within the target and are in effect not trivial to interpret. A reconstruction of the target scattering

body distribution in real space would be an ideal diagnostic tool. Such reconstructions are methodically challenging and a direct inversion of the imaging process is impossible due to the loss of phase information with the measurement [MSC98]. The development of suitable models for the plasma density to reduce the number of free parameters should in principle allow for numerical reconstructions of real space parameter information from experiment data and could thus be key to future high resolution diagnostics of the dynamics associated with LDIA.

2. INTRODUCTION

In an experiment (LN04) that was performed at the Stanford Linear Accelerator Center (SLAC), silicon foil targets with periodic surface structures were studied in a pump-probe setup using the technique of Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) [Klu+17a]. Pulses from an optical UHI laser were focussed on the targets where they produced plasmas of solid density. The plasma dynamical properties were probed by simultaneous irradiation of the interaction volume with an XFEL and the signal was observed on a 2D X-ray photon detector.

In this thesis, the theoretical modeling of the plasma density is presented and a derivation of the predicted intensity patterns is given. The influence of the plasma expansion on the model intensity pattern is studied using various models for the one-dimensional density profiles.

An important goal of this thesis was the design and implementation of a code framework that facilitates the development of structured densities as reduced parameterized models of the target density by providing generic building blocks. Furthermore, it should enable simulations of scattering patterns from these densities that optionally take additional influences on the signal formation, like a non-ideal detector system, into account. The assesment of intensity models attained by the combination of a parameterized density model with a simulation should be possible via freely choosable quality metrics. Through wrapping in a sp-called objective function, the intensity model evaluation and assesment of quality should be made accessible to numerical optimization routines thus providing a completely generic framework for parameter reconstructions of arbitrary densities from scattering signal data.

3. BASICS

In this chapter, basic mathematical definitions are given that are used throughout the thesis. Furthermore, the underlying physical model of the basic image formation process in Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) are recapitulated.

3.1. FOURIER TRANSFORM

Depending on the author and field of science, the mention of the Fourier transform can refer to a bunch of slightly different definitions of this widely used transformation. Unfortunately, it is often not clear from the notation, which convention applies. On the other hand, some equations and theorems have a very simple form if a specific convention is used and sometimes it is desirable to switch conventions within a derivation, which is of course possible. Another reason for the general definition that is shortly given is its usefulness for comparisons with numerical computations of the discrete Fourier transform (DFT), often performed with the Fast Fourier Transform algorithm (FFT). Therefore, for the scope of this thesis, a definition of the Fourier transform is used that allows to explicate the convention at use.

The **Fourier transform** $\mathcal{F}_{a,b}$ and its inverse transform $\mathcal{F}_{a,b}^{-1}$ are here defined for $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ as:

$$\mathcal{F}_{a,b}[f](r) = \sqrt{\frac{|b|}{(2\pi)^{1-a}}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(s) e^{ibrs} ds \quad (3.1)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{a,b}^{-1}[F](v) = \sqrt{\frac{|b|}{(2\pi)^{1+a}}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(w) e^{-ibvw} dw \quad (3.2)$$

and the pair (a, b) is called the **(Fourier transform) convention**.

This definition follows [Weib] In theoretical physics, the convention $(0, 1)$ is most commonly used and simply called "the" Fourier transform. For a function $f(t)$ where t is time, the argument of $\mathcal{F}_{0,1}[f]$ is angular frequency which is usually denoted as ω . Because it is computationally favorable, FFTs usually implicitly employ the convention $(0, -2\pi)$. To keep equations compact, Fourier transforms and inverse Fourier transforms in this work are understood to be

given using the convention $(a, b) = (0, 1)$, if the Fourier operators' lower indices are omitted:

$$\mathcal{F} \equiv \mathcal{F}_{0,1} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\mathcal{F}^{-1} \equiv \mathcal{F}_{0,1}^{-1} \quad (3.4)$$

From (3.1) and (3.2) transformation formulas can be derived to switch between conventions:

$$\mathcal{F}_{c,d}[f](r) = (2\pi)^{\frac{c-a}{2}} \sqrt{\left|\frac{d}{b}\right|} \mathcal{F}_{a,b}[f]\left(\frac{d}{b}r\right) \quad (3.5)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{c,d}^{-1}[F](v) = (2\pi)^{\frac{a-c}{2}} \sqrt{\left|\frac{d}{b}\right|} \mathcal{F}_{a,b}^{-1}[F]\left(\frac{d}{b}v\right). \quad (3.6)$$

For the case of converting between the conventions $(0, 1)$ and $(0, -2\pi)$, (3.5) and (3.6) read:

$$\mathcal{F}_{0,1}[f](r) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \mathcal{F}_{0,-2\pi}[f]\left(\frac{-r}{2\pi}\right) \quad (3.7)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{0,-2\pi}[f](r) = \sqrt{2\pi} \mathcal{F}_{0,1}[f](-r \cdot 2\pi) \quad (3.8)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{0,1}^{-1}[F](v) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \mathcal{F}_{0,-2\pi}^{-1}[F]\left(\frac{-v}{2\pi}\right) \quad (3.9)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{0,-2\pi}^{-1}[F](v) = \sqrt{2\pi} \mathcal{F}_{0,1}^{-1}[F](-v \cdot 2\pi). \quad (3.10)$$

Some equation transformations in this thesis invoke the **convolution theorem**. Its equations have a very simple form using the $(0, -2\pi)$ convention [Weia]:

$$\mathcal{F}_{0,-2\pi}[f * g] = \mathcal{F}_{0,-2\pi}[f] \cdot \mathcal{F}_{0,-2\pi}[g] \quad (3.11a)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{0,-2\pi}[f \cdot g] = \mathcal{F}_{0,-2\pi}[f] * \mathcal{F}_{0,-2\pi}[g]. \quad (3.11b)$$

Employing (3.5), (3.11) can be reshaped to the form that will most often be needed:

$$\mathcal{F}_{0,1}[f * g] = \sqrt{2\pi} \cdot \mathcal{F}_{0,1}[f] \cdot \mathcal{F}_{0,1}[g] \quad (3.12a)$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{0,1}[f \cdot g] = \sqrt{2\pi} \cdot \mathcal{F}_{0,1}[f] * \mathcal{F}_{0,1}[g]. \quad (3.12b)$$

For a clear and efficient way of representing composite one-dimensional functions, further operators besides the Fourier transform are defined. The **reflection operator** \mathcal{S} is defined by:

$$\mathcal{S} : [\mathcal{S}f](x) = f(-x) \quad \forall x, f \quad (3.13)$$

and the operator of **translation by** α , \mathcal{T}_α , is defined by:

$$\mathcal{T}_\alpha : [\mathcal{T}_\alpha f](x) = f(x - \alpha) \quad \forall x, f. \quad (3.14)$$

The scaling of a function's argument axis can elegantly be described with the operator \mathcal{M}_β . β is the factor by which the function graph is scaled along the argument axis and the operator is defined by:

$$\mathcal{M}_\beta : [\mathcal{M}_\beta f](x) = f(x/\beta) \quad \forall x, f. \quad (3.15)$$

Finally, the **Dirac comb distribution** is defined as:

$$\text{III}_T(t) = \sum_{i=-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(t - i \cdot T), \quad (3.16)$$

with the **period** T and the Dirac delta distribution δ . The comb distribution is as also, somewhat laxly, referred to as the comb function.

3.2. THOMSON SCATTERING

This section deals with the scattering of an X-ray photon off a single charged particle. It essentially follows the presentation in [Zac13]. In the initial rest frame of the charged particle, conservation of energy and momentum require the change of photon energy to be of the form:

$$\Delta E_{\text{Ph}} = \Delta p_{\text{Ph}} \cdot c = \frac{p_{\text{Ph},0}^2 \cdot c^2}{m_Q} (1 - \cos(\alpha)), \quad (3.17)$$

where m_Q is the charged particle's mass and α is the photon deflection angle. The change in photon energy described by (3.17) is known as the Compton effect. As can be seen the relative change in photon energy is proportional to the ratio of the photon energy to the particle's rest energy. For photon energies in the order of a few to a few ten keV the photon energy change can therefore be neglected. The case of a photon scattering without changing its energy is called Thomson scattering.

The scattered electric wave field for Thomson scattering can be derived in a classical model and this derivation yields the same results as the exact quantum mechanical description. The formula that will shortly be given for the scattering off an electron is based on the following definitions: Prior to the interaction with the incoming planar wave \mathbf{E}_{in} , the electron is at rest in the point of origin. \mathbf{E}_{in} is polarized in the direction $\mathbf{E}_{\text{in}}/|\mathbf{E}_{\text{in}}| = \mathbf{e}_{\text{in}} = \mathbf{e}_x$ and has the wave vector $\mathbf{k} = |\mathbf{k}|\mathbf{e}_z$. The scattered wave is observed at \mathbf{r} , the unit vector of the polarization of the scattered wave is denoted as \mathbf{e}_{sct} . For Thomson scattering off an electron, \mathbf{E}_{sct} is given by [Jac75; Sch01]:

$$\mathbf{E}_{\text{sct}} = - \underbrace{\left(\frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 m_e c^2} \right)}_{r_e} \frac{\exp(i|\mathbf{k}||\mathbf{r}|)}{|\mathbf{r}|} \underbrace{[\mathbf{e}_{\text{in}} - (\mathbf{e}_{\text{in}} \cdot \mathbf{e}_r) \mathbf{e}_r]}_{\rho \cdot \mathbf{e}_{\text{sct}}} |\mathbf{E}_{\text{in}}|. \quad (3.18)$$

In (3.18), r_e is the classical electron radius and ρ is called polarisation factor.

To obtain the cross section σ_{Th} , the absolute square of (3.18) is taken. Then the scattered X-ray intensity $I_{\text{sct}} = |\mathbf{E}_{\text{sct}}|^2$ is normalized to the incoming intensity $I_{\text{in}} = |\mathbf{E}_{\text{in}}|^2$ and integrated over $dA = r^2 d\Omega$ (3.18), yielding:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\text{Th}} &= \frac{I_{\text{sct}} \cdot r^2 d\Omega}{I_{\text{in}}} \\ &= r_e^2 \rho^2 d\Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

The differential Thomson cross section can immediately be seen to be:

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)_{\text{Th}} = r_e^2 \rho^2. \quad (3.20a)$$

Using common polar coordinates in which \mathbf{r} is characterized by $|\mathbf{r}|$, θ and ϕ , (3.20a) can be brought into the form:

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right)_{\text{Th}} = r_e^2 \left[1 - \sin^2(\theta) \cos^2(\phi)\right] \quad (3.20b)$$

3.3. SMALL ANGLE X-RAY SCATTERING

In a SAXS experiment, the scattering pattern is the result of the interference of photons from an at least partially coherent pulse off a distribution of scatterers. Due to the ratio of the cross sections, usually electrons dominate the signal. However, if the X-ray energy is tuned to an atomic transition thereby enhancing the according cross section by orders of magnitude, the ion distribution becomes important. The following discussion is in principle untouched by the species of scatterers, up to constant scaling factors. For simplicity it is given exemplarily for free electrons.

In the range of keV to few ten keV photon energy, Thomson scattering is the dominant scattering process. Using (3.18), it is in principle possible to compute the X-ray field \mathbf{E}_{sct} on the detector without any assumptions, provided the distribution of electrons ρ and the wave function of the incident XFEL pulse, \mathbf{E}_{in} , are known. Here, ρ is a sum of delta distributions at the positions of the individual electrons and has the unit of a number volume density. Practically this general approach is impossible for all but the simplest cases. However, employing some reasonable assumptions, \mathbf{E}_{sct} can be brought into a simple form. Its derivation and preconditions are outlined now.

The incident X-ray field \mathbf{E}_{in} is treated as a plane wave. Therefore, the differences between the wave phases the electrons experience at their individual positions are fixed for all times and positions which is equivalent to stating that the X-ray is fully coherent. All electrons interact only with this incident field and according to (3.18). This second assumption implies that the interaction between a photon and the electron distribution is limited to single scattering. Finally, the distance between target and detector is assumed to be much larger than the distances between all electrons in the target, so \mathbf{E}_{sct} is studied in the far field.

Neglecting the unscattered part of the incident X-ray field, the wave field at the position \mathbf{r} on the detector is the superposition of elementary waves originating from scattering events at all positions \mathbf{r}' in the target. The contribution from a single \mathbf{r}' is correctly described by replacing $\mathbf{r} \rightarrow \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'$ in (3.18), if an electron is present. This condition is accounted for by adding the factor $\rho(\mathbf{r}')d^3r'$. Due to the far field approximation, $\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}' \approx \mathbf{r}$ except for the complex exponential which is the phase factor and varies significantly on the scale of the electron distribution. It can be split into two terms: $\exp(i|\mathbf{k}||\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|) = \exp(i|\mathbf{k}||\mathbf{r}|) \cdot \exp(-i\mathbf{q}\mathbf{r}')$. Of these, only the second factor depends on \mathbf{r}' .

The contribution of a volume element in the target to the field on the detector now reads as:

$$d\mathbf{E}_{\text{sct}}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = -r_e \frac{\exp(i|\mathbf{k}||\mathbf{r}|)}{|\mathbf{r}|} \rho(\mathbf{r}) e_{\text{sct}}(\mathbf{r}) |\mathbf{E}_{\text{in}}| \cdot \exp(-i\mathbf{q}\mathbf{r}') \rho(\mathbf{r}') d^3r' \quad (3.21)$$

and integration of $d\mathbf{E}_{\text{sct}}$ over the target volume yields the X-ray field on the detector:

$$\mathbf{E}_{\text{sct}}(\mathbf{r}) = -r_e \frac{\exp(i|\mathbf{k}||\mathbf{r}|)}{|\mathbf{r}|} \rho(\mathbf{r}) e_{\text{sct}}(\mathbf{r}) |\mathbf{E}_{\text{in}}| \cdot \underbrace{\int \exp(-i\mathbf{q}\mathbf{r}') \rho(\mathbf{r}') d^3r'}_{\mathcal{F}_{0,1}[\rho](-\mathbf{q})} \quad (3.22)$$

Finally, the differential cross section can be derived similarly to (3.20):

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right) = \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right)_{\text{Th}} \cdot |\mathcal{F}[\rho](-\mathbf{q})|^2 \quad (3.23a)$$

$$= r_e^2 \left[1 - \sin^2(\theta) \cos^2(\phi)\right] \cdot \left|\int \exp(-i\mathbf{q}\mathbf{r}')\rho(\mathbf{r}')d^3r'\right|^2. \quad (3.23b)$$

So far, no restrictions on the observation angles have been made. If they are small, that is: $\sin(\theta) \approx \theta \approx 0$, (3.23) simplifies to:

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega}\right) = r_e^2 \cdot |\mathcal{F}[\rho](-\mathbf{q})|^2 \quad (3.24)$$

and q_x, q_y are linearly proportional to the pixel position on the detector.

4. METHODS

4.1. THE EXPERIMENT

The scattering images that are discussed in this work have been measured during a campaign at SLAC in October 2016. In this section, the implementation of these experiments is described. The experiment setup can be seen in figure 4.1.

To study the plasma expansion into vacuum, a pump-probe mode of operation has been employed [Klu+17a] [Klu]: An UHI laser is focussed to a spot of approximately $16\ \mu\text{m} \times 30\ \mu\text{m}$ (FWHM) on a silicon foil, irradiating it under an angle of 45 degrees with $5 \cdot 10^{18}\ \text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ for the pulse duration of 80 fs and by its interaction with the foil produces a plasma of solid density. An XFEL pulse of 40 fs duration containing 10^9 to 10^{12} photons of 8 keV energy is focussed on the same foil region to a spot of approximately $5 - 10\ \mu\text{m}$ (FWHM), travelling perpendicularly to the UHI laser and also irradiating the foil under an angle of 45 degrees. By scattering off it, the X-ray pulse picks up information about the plasma state. After penetrating the foil, it propagates to the detector, a *PIXIS-XF: 2048B* camera and the intensity on the detector is converted to an image of 2048×2048 pixels. The direct beam is blocked. By tuning the time delay between the arrival of the two pulses, it is in principle possible to study the effect of plasma expansion on the scattering signal at different times after the irradiation with the UHI laser. After the experiment it was realized that the performance of the timing tool responsible for the precise measurement of the time delay was not good enough to allow for an analysis of the temporal evolution of the expansion in the sense of an expansion velocity [Klu].

The targets were silicon foils of $2\ \mu\text{m}$ thickness with a periodic grating of rectangular ridges with a height in the order of 100 nm on top. They are depicted in figure 4.2. Gratings of different periods g and ridge widths b were used. The experiment shots that were analysed in this work were performed with gratings that had the design parameters $g = 300\ \text{nm}$ and $b = 150\ \text{nm}$.

For each target at first two SAXS measurements were taken at reduced XFEL intensity without UHI laser pulse. These [Klu] Only then the pump-probe measurement was taken which in the process destroyed the target.

The detector, was placed 145 cm behind the target and perpendicular to the path of the XFEL pulse. The full width of detected values of q was therefore $0.768\ \text{nm}^{-1}$ in each axis' direction and was resolved by 2048×2048 pixels. The resulting Δq of one pixel is $3.75 \cdot 10^{-4}\ \text{nm}^{-1}$. The camera's point spread function (PSF) was measured to have a σ of $\approx 33\ \mu\text{m} = 2.44\ \text{px}$ [Las].

Figure 4.1.: The LN04 experiment setup. The right-handed coordinate system x, y, z is defined by the XFEL (z) and UHI laser (x) propagation directions. For the target's description, the by 45° rotated system u, v, w is useful.

Figure 4.2.: Schematic depiction of a target foil with the parameter names that are used throughout this thesis: b is the width of a single ridge, g is the periodicity length.

Figure 4.3.: Logarithmic plot of the shots that have been used for analyses. The areas overlaid in green are masked out.

4.2. THEORETICAL CLASSIFICATION OF THE EXPERIMENT

The experiments performed at SLAC were designed to study the effect of plasma expansion with laser-driven solid density plasmas using SAXS. In order to enable interpretations of the experimental findings with regard to expansion, this section explains how the relevant plasma properties were modelled taking into account the specific target design.

Considering the experimental setup, the formation of the detector signal can be described like this: The XFEL pulse enters the target and interacts with the plasma, thereby generating the exit pulse which propagates to the detector. By interaction with the detector, the exit pulse is transformed to the detector signal.

It is obvious that only plasma properties can be detectable that take part in the interaction with the entry pulse and that thereby distinguishably influence the state of the exit pulse. A suitable plasma model therefore needs to represent the dominant of those properties.

Aside from photoelectric absorption, the predominant interaction process of the XFEL with the silicon target is coherent scattering as described by (3.18) and (3.20b) [13]. This stays true as the matter transits to the plasma state. From the detector dimensions and its distance from the target, it can be deduced that the small angle approximation holds. To determine, whether the approximation of single scattering is appropriate, the scattering probability is estimated. It is equal to the total cross section normalized by the irradiated target area A . The target's total cross section is proportional to the total number of electrons in the irradiated volume $V\rho$. Furthermore: $d\sigma = (d\sigma/d\Omega)_{\text{Th}} d\Omega \leq r_e^2$, which yields:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma &\leq V \cdot \rho \cdot r_e^2 \cdot 4\pi \\ &= V \cdot 5.03 \cdot 10^{31} \text{ m}^{-3} \cdot 7.94 \cdot 10^{-30} \text{ m}^2 \cdot 4\pi \\ &= V \cdot 5.02 \cdot 10^3 \text{ m}^{-1}.\end{aligned}$$

Taking into account the incident angle of 45 degrees, the relevant target volume is $V = A \cdot d = A \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot 2 \mu\text{m}$, leading to the scattering probability:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\sigma}{A} &\leq d \cdot 5.02 \cdot 10^3 \text{ m}^{-1} \\ &= 1.42 \cdot 10^{-2}.\end{aligned}$$

The probability of multiple scattering is estimated as that of single scattering to the power of the multiplicity. Already for double scattering this probability is at least two orders of magnitude lower and is therefore neglected. For (3.24) to be a good description of the scattering pattern, the X-ray pulse must be sufficiently coherent, which is fulfilled for X-ray pulses generated by an XFEL [Var+11]. Therefore, (3.24) is a good description of the scattering pattern

Due to the upper limit of detected scattering angles, the electron positions can be resolved down to approximately 10 nm. The scattering signal of structures of a smaller scale would only show up at larger q which are not captured by the detector. Describing the electron volume density with a resolution of 10 nm or finer is therefore sufficient.

The detection process integrates the X-ray intensity over the direction of the pulse, that is: over q_z , and over its full duration. Integration over q_z implies that no information of the density's structure in z direction is encoded in the measured intensity pattern. Therefore, the relevant density can be modelled as the electron area density obtained by projection of the

volume density along z :

$$\rho_A(x, y) = \int_{z, \text{XFEL path}} \rho_V(x, y, z') dz', \quad (4.1)$$

Accordingly, the 2D scattering signal is treated to originate from that area density.

Regarding the time integration, the electron area density must in principle be treated to be time dependent, if the plasma is not static during its interaction with the X-ray photons. In the case, by the integration over the pulse time, the XFEL accumulates expansion information from an evolving plasma state. This fundamentally limits the resolution of expansion scale parameters deduced from the scattering signals to the scale of the advance of expansion during the pulse duration.

4.3. TARGET SPECIFIC DENSITY MODEL

The target design that was used in the LN04 experiments promotes some simplifications for an approximative description of the electron area density, which is here referred to as the density function.

Due to the grating structure, the density function is independent of the coordinate u , compare figure 4.1. In a normalized description, it can thus be treated as a line density, denoted as $\rho(v)$. Furthermore, taking into account the periodicity of the grating, this line density can be expressed as:

$$\rho(v) = (\text{III}_g * R)(v) + \text{const}, \quad (4.2)$$

where g is the grating period and R is the ridge function that describes a single ridge's density profile and vanishes for $v \rightarrow \pm\infty$. The density function and its constituents are depicted in figure 4.4. The constant value accounts for the homogenic density background that is due to the foil. The ridge function is decomposed into separate left and right edge functions E_{left} and E_{right} for the ascending and descending density, respectively, like this:

$$R(v) = \mathcal{T}_{-b/2} E_{\text{left}}(v) + \mathcal{T}_{b/2} \mathcal{S} E_{\text{right}}(v), \quad (4.3)$$

where b is the width of one grating ridge. To make sure that R in this equation tends towards zero outside the ridge, edge functions are here required to fulfill:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\text{left}}(v) &\xrightarrow{v \rightarrow \pm\infty} \pm c_\infty \\ E_{\text{right}}(v) &\xrightarrow{v \rightarrow \pm\infty} \pm c_\infty \end{aligned}$$

with a constant c_∞ . Using (4.3), (4.2) can be transformed to:

$$\rho = \mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \text{III}_g * E_{\text{left}} + \mathcal{T}_{b/2} \text{III}_g * \mathcal{S} E_{\text{right}} + \text{const}. \quad (4.4)$$

Figure 4.4.: From top to bottom: The ridge function R ; the delta comb with period $g = 4$; the periodic density $\rho = \text{III}_g * R$; another periodic density $\rho_2 = \text{III}_g * R_2$ with a more smeared out ridge for which the tails start to overlap. The black curves are the constituent single ridges.

4.4. TARGET SPECIFIC INTENSITY MODEL

As has been discussed in section 4.3, the target foils' structure allows for a one-dimensional approximate description of the electron density in the form of (4.4). To derive its expected scattering pattern in accordance with (3.24), now the Fourier transform and the absolute square thereof are applied to this ansatz.

The Fourier transform of the density (4.4), after application of the convolution theorem (3.12) and transformation rules of \mathcal{T} and \mathcal{S} , reads as:

$$\mathcal{F}[\rho] = \sqrt{2\pi} \left\{ \mathcal{F}[\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \text{III}_g] \cdot \mathcal{F}[E_{\text{left}}] + \mathcal{S} \left(\mathcal{F}[\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \text{III}_g] \cdot \mathcal{F}[E_{\text{right}}] \right) \right\} \quad (4.5)$$

and the comb part can directly be evaluated:

$$\mathcal{F}[\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \text{III}_g](q) = e^{-iqb/2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1}{g} \text{III}_{2\pi/g}(q). \quad (4.6)$$

Because III and the edge functions are real functions, the operator \mathcal{S} has the same effect on their Fourier transforms as the complex conjugation \mathcal{CC} :

$$\mathcal{F}[\rho] = \sqrt{2\pi} \left\{ \mathcal{F}[\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \text{III}_g] \cdot \mathcal{F}[E_{\text{left}}] + \mathcal{CC} \left(\mathcal{F}[\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \text{III}_g] \cdot \mathcal{F}[E_{\text{right}}] \right) \right\}. \quad (4.7)$$

So far, left and right density edges were treated independently, so they could still have different shapes. In the experiments, the grating ridges are expected to expand similarly to both sides which suggests the symmetry $E_{\text{right}}(v) = E_{\text{left}}(v) \equiv E(v)$, taking into account that

the reflection of the argument is explicitly denoted in (4.3). With this, (4.7) can be rewritten as:

$$\mathcal{F}[\rho] = \sqrt{2\pi} \{ (1 + \mathcal{C}\mathcal{C}) (\mathcal{F}[\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_g] \cdot \mathcal{F}[E]) \} \quad (4.8)$$

and the Fourier transform's absolute square is therefore:

$$|\mathcal{F}[\rho]|^2 = 2\pi \cdot 4 |\operatorname{Re} (\mathcal{F}[\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_g] \mathcal{F}[E])|^2. \quad (4.9)$$

For edge functions with the symmetry $E = -S E$, (4.4), (4.8) and (4.9) take especially simple forms:

$$\rho = (\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_g - S \mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_g) * E \quad (4.10)$$

$$\mathcal{F}[\rho] = \sqrt{2\pi} \cdot \mathcal{F}[E] \cdot (1 - \mathcal{C}\mathcal{C}) \mathcal{F}[\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_g] \quad (4.11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{F}[\rho]|^2 &= 2\pi \cdot |\mathcal{F}[E]|^2 \cdot 4 |\operatorname{Im} (\mathcal{F}[\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_g])|^2 \\ &= 2\pi \cdot |\mathcal{F}[E]|^2 \cdot G_{g,b}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

Using (4.6), the grating term $G_{g,b}$ is evaluated:

$$\begin{aligned} G_{g,b}(q) &= 4 |\operatorname{Im} (\mathcal{F}[\mathcal{T}_{-b/2} \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_g])|^2 \\ &= 4 \sin^2 \left(\frac{qb}{2} \right) \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{1}{g^2} \mathbb{I}\mathbb{I}_{2\pi/g}^2(q). \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

In figure 4.5, this term and its individual factors are graphed.

(4.12) holds for all q and is the starting point for all following considerations in this section. These considerations deal with $|\mathcal{F}[E]|^2$ which frequently produces terms $\propto \delta(q)$. Also the constant density summand in (4.4) that accounts for the foil produces terms $\propto \delta(q)$ in the Fourier transform. In the experiment $q = 0$ is never observed due to the beam stop. From now on, unless otherwise specified, (4.12) and the equations derived from it are therefore understood to exclude $q = 0$ and terms $\propto \delta(q)$ are omitted.

A simple and instructive edge function that corresponds to the conditions in a perfect cold target is:

$$E(v) = \rho_0 + \rho_1 \cdot \Theta(v), \quad (4.14)$$

where Θ is the Heaviside step function and ρ_0, ρ_1 are constant densities. Since the mapping $f(x) \mapsto f(x) + \text{const}$ does not affect the Fourier transform of f except at $q = 0$, $\rho_0 = 0$ is a valid simplification. Due to the linearity of the Fourier transform, studying (4.14) in normalized form sustains all relevant information. This form now simply reads as:

$$E(v) = \Theta(v) \quad (4.15)$$

with the Fourier transform:

$$\mathcal{F}[\Theta](q) = \frac{i}{q \cdot \sqrt{2\pi}} + \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot \delta(q). \quad (4.16)$$

So for $S = \Theta$, (4.12) becomes:

$$|\mathcal{F}[\rho]|^2 = \frac{1}{q^2} G_{g,b}. \quad (4.17)$$

In first approximation the X-ray intensity signal of the cold grating targets can therefore be

Figure 4.5.: The grating intensity term $G_{a,b}$ and its constituent factors for the range of q that was accessible in the experiments. In the three upper plots, different ideal parameter values for g and b that were approximately realized in the experiment targets are depicted. The Fourier transform of the delta comb appears also as a comb in the scattering pattern whose period scales inversely with the period in position space. As can be seen, the term $\sin^2(qb/2)$ eliminates every second peak in the comb if $g/b = 2$. In the bottommost plot, non-ideal parameters are realized, $g/b \neq 2$. Because this ratio determines the frequency ratio of the comb factor and the sine factor, the minima of the sine factor do not exactly match up with the positions of every second peak in the comb anymore.

expected to vanish like $1/q^2$.

Once the expansion becomes effective the projected electron density is expected to smooth out. At the same time the total number of electrons must stay the same which implies that the total or integrated electron density function is conserved under the smoothing. Mathematically the smoothing of a function that conserves the function's integral over its definition range can be expressed as a convolution with a normalized positive function $\Lambda(x)$ that is localized around $x = 0$. Such Λ is here called a **smoothing kernel**. Reasonable edge functions E can therefore be expressed as:

$$E(x) = (\Theta * \Lambda)(x). \quad (4.18)$$

Note that normalization, localization and positivity imply that Λ vanishes for $x \rightarrow \pm\infty$. Further sensible requirements on Λ for (4.18) to represent a simple smoothing are that Λ shall have exactly one maximum and exactly two inflection points. Kernels Λ that meet these conditions are here called **bell (shaped) curves**. The term is explicitly not reserved for the Gaussian curve which is nevertheless an example for a bell curve and is defined as:

$$f_{Gaussian}(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \quad \sigma > 0. \quad (4.19)$$

After plugging in (4.16) and (4.18), (4.12) reads as:

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{F}[\rho]|^2 &= 4\pi^2 \cdot |\mathcal{F}[\Theta]|^2 \cdot |\mathcal{F}[\Lambda]|^2 \cdot G_{g,b} \\ &= \frac{2\pi}{q^2} \cdot |\mathcal{F}[\Lambda]|^2 \cdot G_{g,b}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.20)$$

It can be concluded that the $1/q^2$ scaling is still effective in scattering images of targets when the plasma expansion has set in. Extending the result found for the perfect cold gratings, another non-periodic q dependent factor, $|\mathcal{F}[\Lambda]|^2$ shows up in the intensity signal. It is linked to the form of the smoothing and its degree.

Identifying $\Lambda = f_{Gaussian}$, (4.20) can further be studied. The Fourier transform of the Gaussian is:

$$\mathcal{F}[f_{Gaussian}](q) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{q^2\sigma^2}{2}}, \quad (4.21)$$

which together with (4.20) yields, for the special case of a Gaussian smoothing:

$$|\mathcal{F}[\rho]|^2 = \frac{1}{q^2} \cdot e^{-q^2\sigma^2} \cdot G_{g,b}. \quad (4.22)$$

Using this result, some qualitative remarks can be made. The Gaussian function (4.19) has a single parameter σ . This parameter controls the width of the function graph in a positively monotonical manner meaning that larger values of σ result in a wider function graph. (4.22) reveals that the term $|\mathcal{F}[\Lambda]|^2$ in (4.20) takes the form of a Gaussian envelope for this choice of Λ . There is a parameter σ' that has exactly the same influence on the intensity envelope Gaussian as a function of q that σ has on the Gaussian that Λ was originally identified with as a function of x . It is found to be $\sigma' = 1/(\sigma\sqrt{2})$. Thus the envelope's width scales exactly with $1/\sigma$.

Also note that (4.20) for $\Lambda = f_{\text{Gaussian}}$ takes a form that is closely related to the error function:

$$S(x) = \Theta(x) * f_{\text{Gaussian}}(x) \quad (4.23)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^{x/(\sigma\sqrt{2})} e^{-\xi^2} d\xi, \quad (4.24)$$

which, with the definition of the error function:

$$\text{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-\xi^2} d\xi \quad (4.25)$$

can be seen to have the form:

$$E(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \text{erf} \left(\frac{x}{\sigma\sqrt{2}} \right) \right]. \quad (4.26)$$

For completeness, the Fourier transform of (4.26) is, in agreement with (3.12), (4.16) and (4.21):

$$\mathcal{F}[E] = \frac{i}{q \cdot \sqrt{2\pi}} \cdot e^{-\frac{q^2\sigma^2}{2}} + \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \cdot \delta(q) \quad (4.27)$$

The derivation that led to (4.22) spurs the following considerations. As was discussed, the smoothing of the step-like edge function with a Gaussian curve implies an envelope term in the intensity that again has Gaussian shape. The parameters controlling their respective widths scale exactly inversely. As a starting point for further analysis it can be suspected that the bell shaped curves Λ responsible for the smoothing generally imply bell shaped detector intensity envelopes $|\mathcal{F}[\Lambda]|^2$. It can also be suspected that the parametrically controlled widths of Λ and $|\mathcal{F}[\Lambda]|^2$ are negatively monotonically linked.

4.5. MODELS OF THE DENSITY PROFILE OF A SINGLE SURFACE

In this section several different edge models are introduced.

According to (4.12) the influence of the edge shape on the detector image can be expressed in terms of its Fourier transform. Section 4.4 also revealed that edge functions that can be expressed as in (4.18) have a Fourier transform that is proportional to $1/q$ as (4.16) assures. The following definitions are given as direct formulas for E rather than explaining Λ and deploying (4.18). In the Fourier transforms the factor $1/q$ from the Θ term shows up nevertheless where (4.18) can be expected to apply.

For the same reasons that were given for the transition from (4.14) to (4.15), the edge models are defined as unitless parameterized functions of a real one-dimensional argument that approach 0, 1 for $x \rightarrow -\infty, +\infty$, respectively. The connection to the experiment is established by plugging in the target coordinate v as defined in figure 4.1 for x . The introduced edge models are parameterized by the value of their first derivatives with respect to x at $x = 0$:

$$\alpha = \left. \frac{dE}{dx} \right|_{x=0}. \quad (4.28)$$

The parameter α is therefore called the edge's **slope**. All here defined E assume their half height at $x = 0$. They are depicted in figure 4.6.

The *normal edge model* is defined as:

$$E_{normal}(\alpha, x) = \frac{1}{2} [1 + \operatorname{erf}(x \cdot \alpha \sqrt{\pi})]. \quad (4.29)$$

Its Fourier transform is:

$$\mathcal{F}[E_{normal}](\alpha, q) = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1}{q} e^{-\frac{q^2}{4\alpha^2\pi}} \quad (4.30)$$

$$= \frac{i\sqrt{2}}{q\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{1}{2} e^{-\frac{q^2}{4\alpha^2\pi}}. \quad (4.31)$$

The according intensity factor has no zeros for all q .

The *sine edge model* is defined as:

$$E_{sine}(\alpha, x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < -\frac{\pi}{4\alpha} \\ \frac{1 + \sin(x \cdot 2\alpha)}{2}, & -\frac{\pi}{4\alpha} \leq x < \frac{\pi}{4\alpha} \\ 1, & \frac{\pi}{4\alpha} \leq x \end{cases} \quad (4.32)$$

Its Fourier transform is:

$$\mathcal{F}[E_{sine}](\alpha, q) = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{1}{q} \frac{2\alpha^2}{4\alpha^2 - q^2} \left(1 + e^{\frac{iq\pi}{2\alpha}}\right) \quad (4.33)$$

$$= \frac{i\sqrt{2}}{q\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{\alpha^2}{4\alpha^2 - q^2} \left(1 + e^{\frac{iq\pi}{2\alpha}}\right) \quad (4.34)$$

The according intensity factor has zeros for:

$$q = \alpha \cdot 2(2k + 1)\pi \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}/\{-1, 0, 1\}. \quad (4.35)$$

The *straight edge model* is defined as:

$$E_{straight}(\alpha, x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < -\frac{1}{2\alpha} \\ x \cdot \alpha + \frac{1}{2}, & -\frac{1}{2\alpha} \leq x < \frac{1}{2\alpha} \\ 1, & \frac{1}{2\alpha} \leq x \end{cases} \quad (4.36)$$

Its Fourier transform is:

$$\mathcal{F}[E_{straight}](\alpha, q) = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{2\alpha}{q^2} \sin\left(\frac{q}{2\alpha}\right) \quad (4.37)$$

$$= \frac{i\sqrt{2}}{q\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{q} \sin\left(\frac{q}{2\alpha}\right) \quad (4.38)$$

The according intensity factor has zeros for:

$$q = \alpha \cdot 2k\pi \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}/\{0\}. \quad (4.39)$$

The *quad* edge model is defined as:

$$E_{quad}(\alpha, x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < -\frac{1}{\alpha} \\ \frac{1}{2}(x \cdot \alpha + 1)^2, & -\frac{1}{\alpha} \leq x < 0 \\ 1 - \frac{1}{2}(x \cdot \alpha - 1)^2, & 0 \leq x < \frac{1}{\alpha} \\ 1, & \frac{1}{\alpha} \leq x \end{cases} \quad (4.40)$$

Its Fourier transform is:

$$\mathcal{F}[E_{quad}](\alpha, q) = \frac{i}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{\alpha^2}{q^3} 2 \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{q}{\alpha}\right)\right) \quad (4.41)$$

$$= \frac{i\sqrt{2}}{q\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{\alpha^2}{q^2} \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{q}{\alpha}\right)\right) \quad (4.42)$$

The according intensity factor has zeros for:

$$q = \alpha \cdot 2k\pi \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}/\{0\}. \quad (4.43)$$

The *gauss* edge model is defined as:

$$E_{gauss}(\alpha, x) = \begin{cases} \exp\left(-\frac{(x \cdot \alpha - \ln 2)^2}{\ln 2}\right), & x < \frac{\ln 2}{\alpha} \\ 1, & \frac{\ln 2}{\alpha} \leq x \end{cases} \quad (4.44)$$

Its Fourier transform is:

$$\mathcal{F}[E_{gauss}](\alpha, q) = e^{iq\frac{\ln 2}{\alpha}} \left(\frac{i}{q\sqrt{2\pi}} + \frac{1}{\alpha} \sqrt{\frac{\ln 2}{8}} e^{-q^2 \frac{\ln 2}{16\alpha^2}} \left[1 - \operatorname{erf}\left(iq \frac{\sqrt{\ln 2}}{2\alpha}\right) \right] \right) \quad (4.45)$$

The according intensity factor has zeros for:

$$q = \left(-\frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{i} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha} \sqrt{\frac{\ln 2}{8}} e^{-q^2 \frac{\ln 2}{16\alpha^2}} \left[1 - \operatorname{erf}\left(iq \frac{\sqrt{\ln 2}}{2\alpha}\right) \right] \right)^{-1} \quad (4.46)$$

Obviously the influence of α on the model functions is bound to the respective models. The slope α therefore has no immediate physical meaning and it is to be expected that for varying models, different values of α are the most appropriate ones in describing a fixed true density profile within the model. Of course plugging the same α into different models provides that the resulting edge functions have the same tangent at $x = 0$. As the edge functions are used to describe the density profile of an expanding plasma surface, it is purposeful to interpret $1/\alpha$ as the width of E . In this sense, the quantity $1/\alpha$ is a scale length of the expansion. It is the difference in x of the two intersection points of the tangent at $x = 0$ with the horizontal lines $y = 0, y = 1$. For the reasons mentioned above, $1/\alpha$ is not assured to be a model independent physically characteristic scale length of the expansion.

Figure 4.6.: **Top:** The different edge functions evaluated with $\alpha = 1$. **Bottom:** Detailed view. The point reflected *gauss* edge function differs from the original shape.

Figure 4.7.: Logarithmic plot of the absolute squares of the edge functions' Fourier transforms, evaluated for the value of α that in the *normal* edge model corresponds to $\sigma = 5$ nm. The q axis reflects the detected q range in one direction in the experiments. The relative differences between the different edge shapes are largest for high values of q .

4.6. MEASURES OF THE EXPANSION WIDTH

The model functions introduced in section 4.5 are used to approximate the true expanded density profiles in the experiment. To relate model information from these density edge models to the physics of expansion, expansion scale lengths or widths are derived from the model edge shapes. In section 4.4, the term width was used interchangeably with the parameter σ of the Gaussian kernel which by the derivation given there can also be applied to the edge function (4.27).

For the study of general edge functions, the concept of a width is purposefully defined independently of specific model parameters. Such width can be used to characterize and compare model information between different edge models which qualifies them as candidates for physically meaningful expansion scale lengths. Here, a **width** is understood as a function w mapping from an edge or bell function f to its definition range which has the unit of a length for the density functions and scales with the argument of f :

$$w(\mathcal{M}_a f) = a \cdot w(f). \quad (4.47)$$

This definition is of course not unique, different width functions can be defined. The use of the term width for the σ of the Gaussian in section 4.4 is consistent with (4.47): The mapping from Gaussian kernels (4.19) to their parameter σ is a width in this sense. Also the inverse slope of the edge models discussed in section 4.5 is consistent with (4.47).

A parameterized family of width functions w_β is defined specifically for normalized edge functions $E : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ as:

$$w_\beta(E) := E^{-1}(0.5 + \beta) - E^{-1}(0.5 - \beta), \quad (4.48)$$

Figure 4.8.: The relation between the parameter β and the edge width function w_β specified by it.

where E^{-1} is the reverse function of E and β is the parameter. These width functions measure the abscissal distance between the two points on the function graph where the horizontal lines at $0.5 \pm \beta$ are intersected. They are well-defined widths of edge functions in the sense of (4.47) if and only if the edge function is strictly monotonical between the horizontal lines at $0.5 \pm \beta$. For the edge models defined in section 4.5 this is the case for $\beta \in [0, 0.5)$. The relation between β and w_β is depicted in figure 4.8.

If for a fixed edge function E the values of two different specific width functions u , w are known, their ratio can be calculated. (4.47) ensures that this ratio is the same for the so defined widths of $\mathcal{M}_a f$ for all a :

$$\frac{u(E)}{w(E)} = \frac{u(\mathcal{M}_a E)}{w(\mathcal{M}_a E)}. \quad (4.49)$$

For the comparison of two different edge function shapes it useful to transform the functions so that their secants defined by the intersection points with the horizontal lines at $0.5 \pm \beta$ coincide between the models. The remaining degree of freedom can be fixed by the choice of the secant's slope γ . The parameter α that realizes the width $2\beta/\gamma$ for the model of interest can for example be calculated from the width w_β this model edge function has for $\alpha = 1$:

$$\alpha(\beta, \gamma) = \frac{\gamma \cdot w_\beta(\alpha = 1)}{2\beta}. \quad (4.50)$$

This transformation is illustrated in figure 4.9. By use of (4.50), the degree of expansion and the specific width metric can in analyses be varied independently of one another: The parameter γ determines the degree of expansion and β determines the metric. The concrete value of the width defined by both parameters is $2\beta/\gamma$.

The function that maps the edge function (4.26) to the width 2σ can be interpreted as a special case of (4.48) with $\beta = 0.3413\dots = \text{erf}(1/\sqrt{2})/2$. In order to find the parameter α of an arbitrary edge function that realizes $w_{0.34\dots} = \sigma$ using (4.50), the additional requirement is $\gamma = \beta/\sigma = \text{erf}(1/\sqrt{2})/(2\sigma)$.

Figure 4.9.: **Top:** The edge function of interest, evaluated for $\alpha = 1$ and its width w_β for some value of β . **Middle:** The intended width as defined by β and the secant's slope γ . **Bottom:** The adapted edge function whose secant matches the parameters and the slope of its target at the point of origin.

4.7. MEASURES OF INTENSITY MODEL QUALITY

To judge the quality of a model of a measured intensity pattern, measuring functions are used. A measuring function or quality measure quantifies the amount of disagreement between model and experimental result. It takes both intensity patterns, which are functions of the scattering vector q and are commonly represented in discrete form as pixel images, and maps them to the positive real axis. If model and experiment are in perfect agreement in the sense implied by the quality measure, its value is zero. Higher values represent increasing disagreement and thereby suggest that the model is less appropriate to describe the data.

A quality measure of pixel image intensities has to accumulate the information that is encoded in all pixels. Therefore model and data are compared pixelwise by some function and the values for all pixels are gathered for example by summing them up. If changes in the quantity of interest effect the same amount of change in the pixel intensities for all pixels and if furthermore the random measuring errors are Gaussian distributed for all pixels independently and with the same parameter σ , the sum of the squared differences of the pixel intensities between model and data is a good quality measure. Otherwise for example weighted measures can be more appropriate as they can have a higher sensitivity to the quantity of interest. Weighting factors that depend on q or the model or data intensities themselves can also enhance the signal to noise ratio for the quality measure.

The model of the LN04 scattering images causally links the pixel intensities to the density model parameters. With regard to plasma expansion, the model parameter α of the models presented in section 4.5 whose inverse $1/\alpha$ can be interpreted as an expansion scale length is the quantity of interest. To estimate the influence of a change of the expansion scale length, the derivative of the intensity envelope term that is the squared absolute value of (4.31) of the *normal* edge function is taken with respect to $1/\alpha$. It is:

$$\frac{d|E_{\text{normal}}(q)|}{d(1/\alpha)} = -\frac{1}{2\pi^2} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha}. \quad (4.51)$$

If the other model parameters are assumed as fixed, the change in intensity due to a change in the expansion width is therefore independent of q . This means, if the model accurately describes the data except for a small deviation of the model expansion width from its true value, this deviation shows up as a constant summand in the intensity envelope in each pixel. Because the envelope itself drops fast for higher values of q , the relative change in intensity dI/I is larger for higher q . Therefore $(\Delta I/I)^2$ is more sensitive to the expansion scale length than $(\Delta I)^2$. Another argument that favors $(\Delta I/I)^2$ is the error introduced by disregarding the sine term in (4.13) from the ridge width. If the model assumes an inaccurate value for the ridge width, this term implies that the modelled photon number is off by a number that is proportional to the envelope and hence is for low q large compared to the effect caused by a change in the expansion scale.

4.8. COMPARISON OF INTENSITY ENVELOPES OF VARIOUS DENSITY PROFILES

From the treatment of the model intensity pattern in section 4.4 it is clear that the envelope term that is induced by the shape of the density edge contains the expansion information. The parameterized density profiles introduced in section 4.5 predict different envelope func-

tions. To form the basis of further analysis, these envelopes are here qualitatively compared for various values of the parameters β and γ that are explained in 4.6. The values for γ were chosen to match existing reconstruction results from a single model approach [Röd].

The considered situations are depicted in figure 4.10. As the expansion advances, the graphs of the envelopes are compressed along q . The compression factor is the same for all models as is expected due to (4.50). Therefore, the relative position of the zeros of each model stay the same with regard to the other models' zeros. The comparison of the pairs of plots that implement the same expansion scale parameter value but equalize the widths at different densities shows that the relative positions of the zeros are sensitive to changes in β . Furthermore, for the larger value of β , all zeros are moved towards higher q (models *sine*, *quad*) or stay the same (model *straight*).

Figure 4.10.: The intensity envelope terms $|\mathcal{F}[E]|^2$ are depicted for the different models over the q axis that was accessible in the LN04 experiments. Between the plots, the values of the expansion scale parameter γ and of the secant height parameter β which determines the equalized width metric are varied: **The upper three plots** show the envelopes for equalized widths at the normalized densities 0.2, 0.8 and expansion scales corresponding to $\sigma = 6 \text{ nm}$, 8 nm , 10 nm , respectively. **In the lower three plots**, the same values for sigma are used and the widths are equalized at the normalized densities 0.1, 0.9. For γ , the corresponding values of σ in (4.26) are given. Additionally to the envelopes, their zeros are marked by the dashed lines.

4.9. THE RECONSTRUCTION CODE

An important goal was the reconstruction of the electron density in the target from the experimentally measured SAXS intensities. Most generally speaking, reconstruction algorithms are used to determine candidate values of the quantity of interest that agree with the results of an experiment. They require a model of the measurement process that describes the causal connection between the quantity of interest and the experimental result. Here, the distribution of electrons in the target is the quantity of interest and the measured SAXS pattern is the experimental result. For the considered SAXS experiments, the suitability of (3.24) as causal model was made plausible. It could also be seen that describing the distribution of electrons by an area density is adequate. The specific form of representation of the area density is called the density model.

As the phase problem renders a direct inversion of (3.24) impossible, only techniques that solely rely on the forward mapping from the density to its expected scattering pattern qualify for the density reconstruction. In a common approach, scattering patterns are simulated for density candidates that are for example guessed. These simulated scattering patterns are then compared to the experimental result using a so called objective function. An objective function is a measure for the degree of disagreement between a simulated and a detected scattering pattern. Therefore, with respect to the objective function, the density candidate that yields the smallest value is considered the best estimate of the unknown true density. By combination with a minimization algorithm, the objective function can thus be used to construct a reconstruction algorithm.

It is clear, that in order to reconstruct the density with a computer algorithm, a suitable density model must be chosen. So far, the density was modelled as a function of position without regard to the involved number of degrees of freedom. If arbitrary density functions are allowed, there are infinitely many degrees of freedom. In order to define density models that are accessible for computer reconstruction algorithms, restrictions have to be made. A set of 2D functions with a finite number of degrees of freedom are discrete representations or pixel images, that have a fixed number and size of pixels where each pixel stores one density value. In such model, the density resolution is of course limited. But this is acceptable because the detected scattering pattern already imposes an upper and a lower limit on the resolution. Furthermore, the structures that are of interest in the experiments have a specific scale range and can therefore be resolved by using an appropriate pixel size. Nevertheless, as the variable density representation in a reconstruction algorithm, a pixel model still poses a problem: The high degree of underdetermination that is due to the loss of phase information.

The obvious approach to overcome the problem of underdetermination is reducing the number of variables that are used to represent the density. This could be achieved by choosing a coarser resolution which is however not a suitable solution: It undermines the purpose of a high resolution reconstruction and also would probably not lead to better convergence because a larger pixel size in the target domain basically means that in the scattering pattern, intensity values at higher q are ignored. In the present work, another idea was pursued: The density function's number of degrees of freedom is limited to a fixed small number by introducing shape conditions as additional a-priori knowledge. This is achieved by defining it as a parameterized function of position whose shape is completely determined by the choice of parameter values. Such function definition is from now on called a parameterized model and its parameters are referred to as the model parameters. It can readily be seen that the high degree of symmetry in the target shape implies an area density that lends itself to this kind of

modelling which was a major objective for this design. In fact, (ρ) already contains two model parameters in the form of g and b . The terms that remain to be defined in parameterized form in order to obtain a parameterized density model in the explained sense are the edge functions. They are the really interesting parts because their reconstructed shape provides information about the plasma expansion state.

A code base consisting of several packages was developed in Python for setting up customized reconstruction routines for the measured SAXS data. The code base aids the design and implementation of parameterized area and line density models as well as of the experiment model which is represented as successive functional steps. Furthermore it provides a means to wrap density model and experiment model up to form an objective function of the model parameters. The intensity data obtained in the experiments has the form of image data. As input to the reconstructions, raw image data was used as well as preprocessed data, which had been subjected to different preprocessing steps as for example background subtraction and masking. For the proper comparability of simulated and experimental intensity patterns in the objective function, additional preprocessing steps like axis alignment and cropping were applied to the input data before starting the minimization routine. In the following subsections, the code parts are described.

4.9.1. DENSITY PACKAGE

As has been seen, area density functions of two spatial coordinates are adequate for the treatment of the scattering patterns. Furthermore, these area densities are assumed to be approximately independent of the coordinate that runs parallel to the ridges and grooves. The remaining function of one coordinate is approximately a periodic repetition of a shape that represents a groove followed by a ridge and the ridge can further be decomposed into a rising and a falling edge.

A code package was developed in python that provides classes for flexibly implementing density functions that are suitable models for the electron densities in LN04. The package aims to guide and simplify the design of density functions for which the mentioned approximations apply. At the same time, it tries to be general, necessitating only little extensions to also support a wider range of density functions. As this package is part of the simulation and reconstruction code base that was implemented, a main design goal from a programming point of view was to allow for model adjustments without major changes in the rest of the code.

The base classes that were defined in the density package are two functors, one for line densities that are functions of one coordinate (1D functor) and one for area densities that are functions of two coordinates (2D functor). Both 1D and 2D functor implement the special method `__call__` by passing their respective coordinate argument(s) to another method that has to be present in the functor instance.

The only derived 2D functor, `Wrap1dTo2d`, is designed to wrap an arbitrary 1D functor that it takes as an argument on instantiation, along with another function. That other function maps the two coordinates that are passed to `Wrap1dTo2d`'s instance to one single coordinate that is then handed down to the wrapped 1D functor whose return value is propagated as `Wrap1dTo2d`'s return value. The mapping function defaults to the first of the two coordinate arguments, thereby providing a simple means to instantiate from a 1D functor a 2D functor that only depends on the first coordinate. By providing a customized coordinate mapping, the `Wrap1dTo2d` instance can be made to only depend on the second coordinate, a linear

Figure 4.11.: 1: Program model of a single processing step in the simulation of the intensity pattern: Immutable input in the form of the model variables and the model constants is used by the simulation item as well as the results from prior simulation steps that constitute a mutable state to promote the state towards the simulation result. 2: The full simulation is constituted by linking several simulation items together consecutively. Within the chain, the mutable state is passed down. The first simulation item starts with an empty state and therefore uses only model variables and constants for its computation. The last simulation item is required to bequeath a state that contains the model intensity pattern. 3: In the objective function, all parts are wrapped up: It is initialized with suitably preprocessed experiment intensity data as well as the model constants. To map input values of the model variables to a number that quantifies their representative power in explaining the data, a simulation is combined with a quality measure for the intensity. 4: The objective function can be used to generically set up a reconstruction algorithm by combining it with a numerical minimization algorithm.

combination of both coordinates. It can also be made radially symmetric and so on.

To represent 1D edge shapes that are parameterized by the value of their first derivative at $x = 0$, `Abstract1dEdge` is derived from `Abstract1d`. Specialised edge functors that inherit from `Abstract1dEdge` need to reimplement `__init__` as a function of one argument, otherwise a `NotImplementedError` is raised. Though it is not enforced by the class hierarchy, all edge functors that were implemented share the following properties: For $x \rightarrow \infty$, $x \rightarrow -\infty$, they tend towards or are 0,1, respectively. And at $x = 0$, they attain 0.5. Another 1D functor, `Symmetric1dFromEdge`, wraps an arbitrary `Abstract1dEdge` instance, taking an offset argument at initialisation. Its return values on the negative/positive x axis are those of the edge/mirrored edge, shifted by the half offset to the left/right. Two more 1D functors have been implemented for efficiently creating periodic densities. `Finite1dSection` wraps an arbitrary `Abstract1d` instance, adding upper and lower limits. `Periodic1dFromFinite` wraps an arbitrary `AbstractFinite1d`, from which `Finite1dSection` is derived, and applies a periodic mapping to the coordinate argument before handing it down to its wrapped functor.

4.9.2. SIMULATION WORKFLOW

For the simulation of the scattering images, a code package was developed in python. A base class was defined to represent a single stage in the forming of the scattering pattern. That base class is a general functor class, that takes three arguments, `params`, `interims` and `consts` and has no return value. Conceptually, `params` contains all parameters that are meant to be subject to optimization. On entering the functor, `interims` contains all quantities that have been computed by prior simulation stages. Before returning, the functor adds its own results to `interims`. The `consts` argument represents input quantities that do not depend on `params` and are computed before starting the workflow. They are, like `params`, never changed while objects in `interims` are allowed to be overwritten by later stages.

The density model functor represents a specific parameterized electron density. It takes the definition of the target coordinate arrays from `consts` and the model parameters from `params` and evaluates its density function using these parameters over the target coordinates.

The density function itself is a function from the `dens` module which the density module functor wraps and feeds the specific model parameters to. The returned array of density values is multiplied by a constant factor from `params` and the result is put into `interims`.

The illumination model was introduced to account for a 2D gaussian-shaped envelope of the irradiating electric field of the XFEL on the target. The scale of the gaussian is read from `params`. Using that value in the normalized density function of the gaussian, the envelope is evaluated over the target coordinates defined in `consts` and consequently put into `interims`.

Another model functor applies the illumination by multiplying the density values with the illumination values after reading both arrays from `interims`. The result of the multiplication overwrites the old density array in `interims`.

The process of single Thomson scattering, propagation to the detector in the far field of the target and the transformation to intensity values is modelled by another model functor.

It applies the FFT to the density in `interims`, takes the absolute square of the FFT result and stores the final result in `interims`.

To account for the detector point spread function (PSF), the PSF model was implemented. This model simulates a smoothing of the detector pixel values by convolving them with an array of PSF values from `consts`. The constant PSF values are precomputed from a normalized 2D gaussian with the scale $\sigma = 2.7$ px. The resulting smoothed intensity pattern overwrites the old intensity array in `interims`.

4.9.3. PREPROCESSING

The preprocessing comprises all operations that have to be done once before setting up the objective function and starting the iterative reconstruction.

Several steps deal with the experimental scattering pattern: Typically, the background subtracted image is loaded from file. It is then translated to align the point $q_x = q_y = 0$ in the center of the image and rotated to make the q axes run parallel to the image axes. It is then cropped keeping a centrally aligned rectangular section that contains the peaks. This cropping can significantly decrease reconstruction times without loss in reconstruction quality if the relevant pixel areas are kept.

In order to evaluate the density model during the simulation that is performed in every reconstruction step to compute the value of the objective function, the discretized target coordinates that correspond to the tailored experimental scattering pattern need to be known. They are also created during the preprocessing.

The tailored scattering patterns often still contain pixels whose values are invalid and should be disregarded in computing the objective function. These invalid areas in general have irregular shapes and can for example be due to overexposure or dead pixels. The translation and rotation also creates invalid areas at the tailored scattering pattern's image borders if the new field of view (FOV) contains pixels that are outside the original image's FOV. To distinguish invalid pixels, the objective functions use a boolean mask that is set up during preprocessing and accounts for the mentioned effects. A mask for overexposed pixels had been defined per shot and can be loaded from file. Additionally, a function has been written to automatically determine an overexposure mask from the raw detector images by filtering for the maximum pixel values and adding a pixel safety margin. Another function has been written to automatically determine the mask that accounts for the changed FOV.

In the experiment simulation that is computed during every objective function's evaluation, the detector point spread function (PSF) is another object that is constant and can therefore be precomputed and reused.

4.9.4. THE RECONSTRUCTION SCRIPT

For those reconstructions, the background subtracted data is used as original input. The scattering patterns are tailored to align the q axes parallel to the image axes with $q_x = q_y = 0$ in the image center and then the central section of 2048×8 ($N_{q_y} \times N_{q_x}$) pixels is cropped.

To specify invalid pixel areas, a mask is created that by pixelwise boolean comparison combines the overexposed mask loaded from file with the one that is automatically generated and also with the automatically generated FOV mask.

The detector PSF is precomputed with $\sigma = 36 \mu\text{m} \hat{=} 2.7$ px for 64×64 pixels.

The discretized target domain coordinates are initialized according to the scattering vector range in the tailored scattering pattern as 2048 values in y direction and 8 values in x direction.

The reconstruction script supports several density models. They are implemented as simulation items that read their specific density parameters from `params` and create the discretized 2D density in `interims` by evaluation of a wrapped density function over the discretized target coordinates which are read from `consts`. The wrapped density functions were constructed using the classes described in 4.9.1 and each each model uses a different edge function of those described in 4.5. By design, the 2D density functions have the interval $[0, 1]$ as value range. Therefore the initial discretized 2D density is multiplied with a constant normalization factor A from `params` by the next simulation item.

Additionally to the density model parameters, the parameter σ of a circular 2D gaussian shaped illumination function is reconstructed. The creation of the discretized illumination function and its multiplication onto the density are also implemented as simulation items.

The following simulation steps are fixed, they do not depend on variable parameters that are subject to optimization. The reconstruction parameters are therefore: The grating period g , the ridge width b , the edge function's slope α , the constant normalization factor A and the illumination function's σ .

The employed experiment model consists of:

- multiplication of the density with the illumination function
- scattering and far-field intensity simulation by FFT and absolute square
- convolution with the constant gaussian detector PSF

Figure 4.12.: **Top:** The construction of the 1D grating function. The density profile is described by a function object that is parameterized by α and maps a 1D spatial position to a normalized density value. This function is wrapped by `Symmetric1dFromEdge`, which for positions above $b/2$ implements the reflection on the argument before passing it on to the edge function. `Finite1dSection` is used to "cut" the part of the function that represents the ridge and sets an upper and a lower bound on the argument. `Periodic1dFromFinite` periodically folds the argument it is given to fit into the bounds of the finite function it wraps. **Bottom:** The corresponding 2D grating function attained by wrapping a periodic function 1D function with `Wrap1dTo2d`.

5. RESULTS

The models of the one-dimensional density profile of a single surface introduced in section 4.5 predict different courses of the complex X-ray wave field amplitude in the scattering pattern. The relation of this amplitude to the total scattering pattern has been derived in section 4.4. From this derivation it is clear that, under the assumption of an edge shape that has the symmetry $\mathcal{S} E = -E + \text{const}$, the information about the expansion state of the plasma in the target is encoded in the intensity pattern in the form of a multiplicative term or envelope, that is solely induced by the edge shape. Though the assumption of this symmetry is a simplification that lacks immediate physical justification, it is very useful for the study of model properties in the presented analytical framework. Moreover, it automatically ensures the conservation of density under expansion which for other models, like the presented *gauss* model, might not be the case. The envelope term is imprinted on the periodic peak structure that arises from the target's grating structure and causes a modulation of the peak heights which has the main effect of a damping towards high q and in first approximation scales with q^2 . From sections 4.7 and 4.8 it is evident, that the intensity signal is especially sensitive to changes of the edge shape at high q in the sense that changes here lead to stronger relative intensity differences than at low q . In an interpretation of scattering patterns with regard to the degree of expansion and the specific shape of the plasma density profile at the surfaces it also must be considered that the grating ridges imprint an additional factor on the intensity that takes the form of a periodic damping term. For an ideal grating in which the ridges have a width that exactly equals the half of the grating period, this periodic damping eliminates every second peak that is induced by the grating periodicity. The remaining peaks are in this situation completely unchanged in intensity by the periodic ridge width damping factor as they coincide with its maxima which all have the same height. In the scattering patterns that were detected in the experiment, different degrees of the periodic damping are observed. This complicates the interpretation with regard to plasma expansion as the combined influence of the ridge width damping and the envelope from the edge shape can not easily be separated based on the scattering signal that is effectively sampled by the periodic peak positions. The reconstruction at this sampling rate is further complicated because without knowledge of the exact surface density profile, the envelope term has more than one degree of freedom which suggests that analysis with only a single model of the edge shape that has a single degree of freedom is limited in its explanatory power and reconstruction results may be ambiguous. In reconstructions, especially the reconstruction error on the single expansion parameter and that on the ridge width are suspected to have a relevant co-dependence.

The reconstruction code package that has been developed aims to widen the understanding of scattering patterns by providing a means to efficiently set up varieties of intensity models that should be considered for a given target design. This is achieved through several design decisions:

1. The measurement process is explicitly implemented as a simulation that has the target as an input and computes its intensity pattern on the detector. Thereby, the implementation of the specific target design is made independent of the other aspects of the experiment that are involved in the signal formation.
2. The implementation of target density models is supported by a hierarchy of building blocks that have been implemented and can be extended. This allows for variations of a general target form by changing specific aspects as necessary. During the course of this thesis, the code was used for reconstructions in which this flexibility was exploited to vary the intensity model by varying only the function object that describes the one-dimensional density shape in parameterized form. From the theoretical treatment, this has been seen to be the crucial model component for reconstructions of plasma expansion.
3. The implementation of the simulation that models the interaction and signal formation is supported by building block function objects that perform self-contained simulation steps and can be combined in a chain-like structure to describe the full simulation. Thereby, also the simulation can easily be customized and extended. It is also possible to consider parameters of the signal formation that are not part of the density model as variables in reconstructions. As an example, the σ parameter of a gaussian envelope function of the incident X-Ray field was used as a variable in the performed reconstructions.

Due to its flexibility, the reconstruction code package complements analytical intensity models and enables the fast exploration of various models.

In the next section, the photon numbers in the peaks of the studied data are determined. It is followed by a section that presents results which were achieved with the developed code framework. The final section in this chapter consists of a comparative analysis of the introduced edge functions as candidates for the one-dimensional expanded density profiles.

5.1. DETERMINATION OF PEAK PHOTON NUMBERS

To determine photon numbers from experimental data to which reasonable error bars can be assigned, photons were counted for area surrounding the peak positions. The size of the areas over which the pixel values are summed up must be sufficiently large to include a majority of counting events that were spread out due to the detector's PSF. On the other hand, the signal to noise ratio also increases to the background error if the areas are chosen to big. Here, for peak photon counting, 8×8 pixels have been used. The resulting value was multiplied by a correction factor that accounts for signal that was smeared out beyond the area of integration and was determined by taking the inverse of the integral of the PSF over that area.

For the errorbars, two sources of uncertainty were considered for the detector signal. The first source is the counting nature of the measurement process, the type of uncertainty becomes clear in a simplified description of this process: In each pixel, the X-ray photons are

counted and their total number is the pixel signal. The event of a single photon being counted in a specific pixel is independent of other events of the same type and has constant probability. It is therefore reasonable to assume that the determined photon numbers follow Poisson distributions and are uncertain to the degree implied by this distribution: The standard deviation associated with the photon count N equals \sqrt{N} .

Though the assumption of Poisson statistics is in fact reasonable, the above description neglects the details of the detection process. The following aspects also have to be considered: The x-ray photons illuminate a phosphor on the camera front that converts them to optical photons that are guided to the CCD where they excite electrons. These are converted to counts in analog digital units (ADU) by the camera electronics. The conversion factor from electrons to counts is approximately 1, but the conversion from x-ray photons to counts is 164.88 ± 11.16 ADU [Las]. To consider the Poisson error, the counts in ADU are first converted to number of photons, before the \sqrt{N} error is applied. It should also be considered that the visible light is guided by a fibre that introduces a broadening effect, so that the signal of a single x-ray photon is smeared out over several pixels. The assumption of Poisson distributions is unharmed, if the photon events are localized and photon numbers are determined via integration over appropriate pixel ranges.

The second considered source of uncertainty is due to the detector signal background. This background was experimentally investigated through the measurement of detector signals without an X-ray source. To these measurements, Gaussian distributions had been fitted as the per-pixel background signal distributions. Their standard deviations have only small spread over all pixels and are approximately 15 ADU [Las]. For later analyses, the per-pixel average background signal had been subtracted from the measured scattering patterns. To determine the photon numbers within a single peak, the background subtracted ADU have been integrated over 8×8 pixels. Assuming that the background signals of individual pixels are completely independent of all other pixels, the integral value over 8×8 pixels has a standard deviation of $15 \text{ ADU} \cdot \sqrt{8 \cdot 8} = 120 \text{ ADU}$. Furthermore, the detector's point spread function (PSF) had to be taken into account. It had been approximately determined as a 2D Gaussian with $\sigma = 33 \mu\text{m} \hat{=} 2.44 \text{ px}$ [Las]. The PSF's integral over 8×8 central pixels is 0.80 and therefore the standard deviation of the total photon number in one peak is $120 \text{ ADU} / 0.8 = 150 \text{ ADU} \hat{=} 0.94$ photons. The peak photon numbers and their error bars that were measured for several experiment shots with the described procedure are illustrated along with the scattering signals in figures 5.1 and 5.2.

Figure 5.1.: The determined photon numbers in the peaks with estimated measurement errors for shots 139_1 and 140_1. Also plotted are central lineouts of the background subtracted data from which the numbers were deduced. Masked out pixels are depicted in green.

Figure 5.2.: The determined photon numbers in the peaks with estimated measurement errors for shots 141_1 and 145_1. Also plotted are central lineouts of the background subtracted data from which the numbers were deduced. Masked out pixels are depicted in green.

5.2. RECONSTRUCTION RESULTS FOR PRESOTS

The results shown in this section were obtained from reconstructions of background-subtracted ADU data of several preshots, that had been taken without the UHI laser. For pre-shots, the best signal-to-noise ratio is expected as the grating is yet unperturbed. In this situation, the density profile at the surfaces is ideally steplike. Within the derived model, the normalized intensity envelope from the edge profile predicts the least damping for high q in comparison to measurements when expansion has set in. Reconstructions of preshot data are therefore best suited for an evaluation of the reconstruction method and can show fundamental limitations.

For each shot, one reconstruction run was performed for each density profile model. The pixel representations of the area densities for specific values of the model variables that describe the grating were constructed by evaluation of the grating density function object for the edge model used in the specific run. The grating model variables were:

- the slope parameter α that describes the edge function's first derivative with respect to x at the edge's half-height,
- the grating period g ,
- the width b of a single grating ridge,
- the factor A by which the output values of the normalized density function object are multiplied.

Additionally, the parameter σ of a normalized circular Gaussian illumination function was variable.

In the background subtracted ADU data [Las], those pixels for which the raw data had the highest value in the dynamic range of the camera, were automatically masked out as were pixels within a 20 pixel safety margin of such regions. This mask was combined with one that had been defined by hand per shot, also to account for overflowed pixel regions [Röd]. Utilizing the alignment of prior analysis [Röd] which was cross-checked for the reconstructions here, the central part of 8×2048 pixels of the aligned data which contained the peaks was selected and pixel areas that were invalid due to the changed FOV were also masked out.

The model intensity pixel values for specific values of the reconstruction variables were simulated from the evaluated density pixel values and the pixel representation of the centered circular gaussian illumination function that was evaluated for specific σ . Both pixel arrays were multiplied to simulate a gaussian shaped illumination profile on target. The resulting image was consecutively transformed by Fast Fourier Transformation in accordance with the approximations that apply in SAXS, resulting in an image of complex pixel values that represented the X-ray field on the detector. Of this field, the absolute square was computed and numerically convolved with a circular Gaussian with $\sigma = 36.5 \mu\text{m}$ to account for preliminary results regarding the detector PSF [Las].

The model intensity quality was in the reconstructions measured by:

$$\sum_{\text{FOV}} (I_{\text{data,pixel}} - I_{\text{model,pixel}})^2, \quad (5.1)$$

the sum of the squared intensity differences between data and model, taken over the valid pixels in the selected range. The constituting components were wrapped in an objective

function object, which is illustrated in figure 4.11. When this function is executed, it takes the model variable values as its sole input. The other parameters that enter the calculation are constant and have to be provided at the time of initialization. The objective function evaluates the density model and the illumination function to their pixel representations, performs the simulation of the signal formation and compares the simulation result which is the intensity model with the data the reconstruction is run for by means of the quality measure. The returned value is the model quality that is assigned to the input variables.

For the parameter reconstructions, these objective functions were minimized using the function `basinhopping` from the scientific python library `scipy.optimize` [J+01]. The results of performed reconstruction runs are illustrated in figures 5.3, 5.4, 5.5, 5.6, 5.7, 5.8, 5.9 and 5.10 and are summarized in table 5.1. Judged by the graphs of reconstructed intensities, the reconstructions show a good general agreement with the data. The reconstructed values of the grating parameter g are almost perfectly independent of the utilized edge model as is the ridge width b . Both match the design values within a margin of few nm except for the shot `140_1`. For most runs, the reconstructed values of σ are well above the focus size of the XFEL pulse on target which was in the order of $5 - 10 \mu\text{m}$. The exceptions are the reconstructions of shot `141_1` with the edge models *sine*, *normal* and *straight* which yielded $\sigma = 0.6 \mu\text{m}$. At the high values of σ suggested by most reconstructions, the method would be quite insensitive to changes in σ as the Gaussian is effectively flat over the area it is evaluated for in the simulation performed within the objective function. On the other hand, at $\sigma = 0.6 \mu\text{m}$, influences on the intensity would be non-negligible. Here, no further investigation of the influence of σ was undertaken but would be necessary for conclusive interpretations of the scattering patterns.

The parameter that is connected to the plasma expansion in these reconstructions was the edge slope α . As was discussed in the methods chapter, this expansion parameter inversely scales with the degree of expansion within each model. But for an unknown true density profile it has no immediate physical meaning that allows for assertions about the expansion state which are comparable between models. Indeed, the presented reconstruction results exhibit relative differences of the parameter α between different models in the order of several 10%, for example 38.8% for the reconstructions of shot `139_1` with the models *quad* and *straight*, compare table 5.1. If $1/\alpha$ were a model-independent expansion scale length, the relative difference in α would directly translate to a relative difference of that scale length and so the degree of expansion asserted by the here presented reconstructions with different models would be off between the models but that value.

From these considerations it is obvious that a more sound comparison of the models with regard to the information that can be gained from reconstructions with these models is needed. Such method is approached in the next section. The observations in this section have been of qualitative nature and lack an analysis of the parameter errors based on a theoretical treatment of the influence of measurement errors. It is assumed that in future advances towards conclusively established parameter errors can find a major assist in the developed simulation and reconstruction code package.

Figure 5.3.

Shot	Model	g [nm]	b [nm]	α [nm ⁻¹]	A	σ [nm]
139_1	gauss	298.30	150.04	0.0617	111.37	9.04×10^4
139_1	normal	298.30	150.79	0.0649	111.00	9.08×10^4
139_1	quad	298.30	150.79	0.0681	110.64	9.42×10^4
139_1	sine	298.30	150.83	0.0575	110.50	9.20×10^4
139_1	straight	298.30	150.74	0.0493	110.25	1.03×10^5
140_1	gauss	298.26	169.53	0.0725	88.93	1.38×10^5
140_1	normal	298.27	170.63	0.0742	89.13	6.92×10^4
140_1	quad	298.27	170.63	0.0773	88.99	1.25×10^5
140_1	sine	298.27	170.63	0.0652	88.93	9.37×10^4
140_1	straight	298.27	170.63	0.0558	88.82	8.88×10^4
141_1	gauss	296.87	151.30	0.0608	111.96	1.07×10^5
141_1	normal	297.38	152.80	0.0664	114.63	6.25×10^2
141_1	quad	296.87	152.49	0.0680	111.07	1.26×10^5
141_1	sine	297.38	152.81	0.0587	114.18	6.25×10^2
141_1	straight	297.38	152.83	0.0502	113.96	6.25×10^2
145_1	gauss	298.15	150.46	0.0661	117.97	1.16×10^5
145_1	normal	298.15	151.27	0.0697	117.54	1.13×10^5
145_1	quad	298.15	151.22	0.0729	117.22	9.24×10^4
145_1	sine	298.15	151.33	0.0617	117.11	8.51×10^4
145_1	straight	298.14	151.13	0.0527	116.85	7.75×10^4

Table 5.1.: Reconstruction results: Grating period g , ridge width b , slope α , normalization factor A , illumination function's size σ .

Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.7.

Figure 5.8.

Figure 5.9.

Figure 5.10.

5.3. COMPARISON OF MODELS

As discussed in section 4.8 and illustrated in figure 4.10, the relative differences in the intensity envelope between the models are largest for high values of q . In the introduced intensity models, the parameter α is the one relevant model parameter for expansion as it controls the scaling of the edge model function graphs along the x axis. This parameter has been seen to hold expansion information only relative to the edge model that is considered and therefore has no direct model independent translation to a physically meaningful width that characterizes the degree of plasma expansion. This is confirmed by the reconstructions presented in section 5.2 which produced similar model intensities with values of α whose inverses would suggest degrees of expansion that differ by several 10% between the models.

Here, it is investigated what kind of general statements about the expansion can be made based on scattering data analyses with various different models of the density profile. Rather than analysing intensity data where the true density is unknown, the observations in this section are based on the comparison of model intensities alone. This approach has the advantage that both underlying density profiles are known and conclusions about model and parameter sensitivity to expansion can be drawn more directly than from comparison with data and also no extensive statistical testing is needed. Therefore the method is a good starting point.

All introduced edge models are single parameter models. In fact, it might be possible to reconstruct more than one parameter of the expansion shape from scattering patterns. As a first step it was here investigated if the considered edge models allow for the definition of an expansion scale length that independent of the specific model. For this, the parameterized width measure w_β was used to determine for each model a value of α and the models' predicted intensity envelopes were compared for these α . The model edge function graphs were required to run through two points that thereby defined a secant of the graph and whose positions were fixed by the values of w_β and β , or γ and β , respectively. The meaning of these parameters were explained in section 4.6. The analysis thereby had to parameters, γ or w_β which characterized the expansion scale independently of the model and β which characterized the conversion to the model dependent parameter α .

The parameter β was varied within the full allowed interval (0, 0.5). The parameter γ was determined by comparison with the edge model (4.26) for fixed values of σ . Only the intensity envelope terms are taken into account at the q positions at which peaks are expected for a 300 nm grating as these are the available effective data points in the scattering patterns. In an analysis of experimental data, it would be essential to also take the sine term from (4.13) into account. It is induced by the ridge width and imposes another envelope on the scattering pattern that is periodic and whose influence can not completely be distinguished from that of the envelope implied by the edge density profile a priori. Here, this influence is disregarded and, where experimental data is used in the argumentation, a shot is used that is suitable. Different measures of intensity model quality are considered and compared with regard to their influence on the explanatory power of an intensity model.

In figure 5.11, it can be seen that for the mean of the squared relative intensity differences as the intensity model quality measure, the edge models show the highest pair-wise agreement in intensity, if they are equalized in w_β for values of β around 0.4. This statement is true with only a weak dependence on the expansion scale parameter γ for $\sigma = 3$ nm, 4 nm, 5 nm. In this sense, $\beta \approx 0.4$ and $w_{0.4} = 2 \cdot 0.4/\gamma$ provide the targeted definition of a most model independent measure of the expansion width. For $\sigma = 6$ nm, the quality measure graphs show completely different courses and are orders of magnitude higher. Figure 5.12 reveals

that for the fixed value $\beta = 0.4$, the by far largest contribution to the quality measure comes from the peak of second highest order in visible q . Comparing with figure 5.13, the reason for this high value is evident: It is due to the first envelope zero of the *straight* model which resides close to the peak resulting in a very small reference intensity that by the division produces huge relative differences with the other models. The dropping values of the other envelopes signalize that for this σ also the first zeros of the other models are already close to the range of visible peaks, also compare figure 4.10. Therefore, in this form, the quality measure is not suitable for $\sigma \gtrsim 5$ nm. From a physical point of view this is also clear: In the detector, photons are counted and at or close to zeros of the envelope, the expected value of counted photons is 0. At these q , the relative difference $\Delta I/I$ is not defined and therefore this measure can obtain no information there.

To overcome this limitation, a lower threshold for the normalized reference intensity is determined by comparison with experimental data as illustrated in figure 5.14. As the physical threshold value, the number of 10 photons is chosen. By this choice, also peaks are disregarded that have a comparatively large relative error due to counting statistics and detector background. If in the quality measure only peaks are taken into account, where the reference intensity is above that threshold, the qualitative statement of a most model-independent width measure w_β for $\beta \approx 0.4$ can also be established for $\sigma = 6$ nm as can be seen in figure 5.15.

In an analysis of experimental data by comparison with a model, the choice of the cutoff intensity can be crucial: As was argued, a higher cutoff intensity not only excludes q where the relative intensity difference is not defined but also limits the influence of the relative measurement error which becomes large for low intensities. On the other hand, high cutoff intensities reduce the number of data points and therefore weaken the statistics of the quality measure. Due to the structure of the scattering pattern which consists of peaks that are periodically spaced with $\Delta q = 0.02 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ for $g = 300$ nm, the number of effective data points is already limited and this argument is even stronger for the gratings with smaller period lengths g . For the reconstruction of an expansion width, the loss of data points has a potentially high impact because primarily the values for high q are lost.

The approach of using a lower intensity threshold for masking has also been used in combination with the quality measure $(\Delta I)^2/I$ and the results of the associated pair-wise model comparison are presented in figures 5.16 and 5.17. Here, the value range for σ has been extended to 20 nm. Figure 5.16 suggests that also the quality measure $(\Delta I)^2/I$ supports the statement of a most model-independent width measure w_β for $\beta \approx 0.4$. The statement even seems to hold for larger expansion widths. As figure 5.17 reveals, the model comparison for higher values of σ strongly depends on information contained in a small number of peaks at lower q . It is therefore expected that reconstructions of an expansion width at this level of expansion face strong limitations due to weak statistics and measurement errors.

Summarizing the results from the model comparisons in this section, the parameter value $\beta \approx 0.4$ can be used to define a measure w_β of the expansion width according to (4.48) that has the most model-independent explanatory power for the compared models. Further analysis is needed to study whether, with respect to the measurement errors, the remaining differences between the models allow their distinction in reconstructions of experiment data. Of the considered quality measures, $(\Delta I)^2/I$ seems to be most suitable for reconstructions of expansion scale parameters.

It is important to note that the exclusion of peaks in the computation of the quality measure by application of a threshold intensity can easily be automated it is therefore suitable for

integration in iterative reconstruction algorithms. Though this hasn't been done yet, this quality measure can be implemented in reconstruction code package presented in this work.

Figure 5.11.: The edge model intensity envelopes are compared in pairs. Their deviation from each other is measured by the mean of the squared relative differences taken over the expected peak positions of a 300 nm grating. Along the horizontal axis, the value of β is varied which determines the width measure that is equalized for all edge models. Between the plots, the slope γ of the secant over the equalized width is varied and takes the values that respectively correspond to $\sigma = 3 \text{ nm}$, 4 nm , 5 nm , 6 nm . This figure is complemented by figures 5.12 and 5.13 which illustrate the same parameter setting.

Figure 5.12.: The edge model intensity envelopes are compared in pairs for the same setting as depicted in figures 5.11 and 5.13. Here, the squared relative differences between the models are shown for the fixed value $\beta = 0.4$, plotted over the expected peak positions of a 300 nm grating in the q range accessible to the experiments. Dashed lines are plotted to guide the eye. Note the different vertical scaling in the bottom plot.

Figure 5.13.: The edge model intensity envelopes are plotted over expected peak positions of a 300 nm grating for the same parameters as depicted in figures 5.11 and 5.12. Compare also figure 4.10, which illustrates the positions of the envelope zeros over the continuous q axis.

Figure 5.14.: This is the same plot as in the bottom frame in figure 5.13, overlaid with photon numbers counted for the peaks in experimental data. In the shot that was chosen, the dominant peaks approximately agree with the shapes of the envelopes. To normalize the model envelopes to experimental photon numbers, it is assumed that at the q positions of the dominant peaks the sine term in (4.13) assumes its maximum. The normalized intensity that by comparison with the peak photon numbers corresponds to 10 photons is determined, its value is $I \approx 10^{-1.5} \approx 0.03$.

Figure 5.15.: The same situation and setting of parameters as in figure 5.11 is shown for an adapted measure of intensity model quality: The mean is taken only over peaks in which the reference model's normalized intensity is above the threshold that was determined to correspond to 10 photons peak intensity as shown in figure 5.14. As can be seen, this adapted quality measure restores the graphs' general course that is observed in the upper three in plots in figure 5.11 for the expansion scale $\sigma = 6$ nm for which the first envelope zeros are within the detected q range. The steps in the graphs occur at values of β where the intensity of a peak in the reference model rises above the threshold intensity.

Figure 5.16.: The edge model intensity envelopes are compared in pairs for values of γ that correspond to $\sigma = 4 \text{ nm}, 6 \text{ nm}, 12 \text{ nm}, 20 \text{ nm}$. The measure for the intensity model quality employs the same threshold intensity as that in figure 5.15 which was determined as shown in figure 5.14 and takes the mean of $(\Delta I)^2/I$ over the peaks where the reference model's intensity is above the threshold. The second plot from top comprises the same parameter value for γ as the bottom plots in figures 5.11 and 5.15. As can be seen, for the quality measure used here, the graphs are less sensitive to the influence of single peaks than for $(\Delta I/I)^2$. This figure is complemented by figure 5.17.

Figure 5.17.: The same quality measure and values of σ are used as in figure 5.16. It is depicted for the model pairs over the q values expected for peaks of a 300 nm grating and $\beta = 0.4$. Dashed lines are plotted to guide the eye. Gaps demark peak positions where the reference intensity is below the threshold of 10 photons which are therefore not counted in the masked accumulated quality. As can be seen, $(\Delta I)^2/I$ is more evenly distributed over q than $(\Delta I/I)^2$.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The major motivation for the work that has been presented in this thesis is the goal of a better understanding of the dynamics in solid density plasmas that are used for ion acceleration and driven by UHI short-pulse lasers. Insights to the nm and fs scales of these dynamics has been explained to be the key to the increase of available maximum ion energies and precise control of the beam parameters. Both are crucial for the implementation of LDIA in medical facilities. Recent experiments at XFEL facilities for the first time delivered experimental data that can be analysed for the dynamics at the interesting time and length scales. This data is an ideal test case for the development and assessment of analysis techniques that will be most important for the extraction of parametric plasma information from image data obtained by X-ray scattering from plasmas. The understanding and development of such techniques was the goal of this thesis. A focus was put on the reconstruction of plasma expansion as the experiments had been specifically designed to test for this quantity.

In this work, an analytical description of the target densities has been developed and their predicted scattering images have been derived. From this derivation it is evident that simple analytical descriptions of the intensity in terms of density parameters are only available for highly symmetric models of the expansion profile.

Inspired by the analytical model, a Python module has been developed that allows for the implementation of arbitrary expansion profiles and also has the flexibility for further extension. Another module has been developed for the staged description of simulations of the image formation in coherent X-ray scattering experiments. In combination, the modules can be used to efficiently implement intensity models that are parameterized for properties of the density distribution in the target. Using appropriate measures for the modelled intensity signal and numerical optimization libraries, these parametric intensity models can be harnessed for reconstructions of parametric density information. Thereby, the limitations of analytical intensity models for data analysis can be overcome.

The operation of the reconstruction workflow has been shown for selected shots from the experiment.

The photon numbers in peaks of the experimental shot data have been determined. They were used to normalize the model envelope intensities to allow for the definition of a lower cutoff photon number in the envelope comparison.

A comparison of intensity models that employed different models of the expansion profile has been done. It aimed to establish what kind of additional information can be gained by parallel data analysis with different model expansion shapes. The analysis revealed for

the studied models an expansion measure that is most independent of the specific chosen model. It also revealed, that the assessment of intensity model quality for the intensity patterns of these targets is highly sensitive to the chosen model quality function and also requires careful masking or adaptive weighting of the per pixel intensity qualities.

As a major result of this thesis, the presented framework allows for reconstructions of parameters of arbitrarily defined density models. Thus, it promises to be useful in extracting at a high temporal and spatial resolution the dynamical plasma properties that are linked to instability growth from experiment data.

7. OUTLOOK

The results in this thesis demonstrated the feasibility of the taken approach towards the modelling of target plasma densities and their intensity patterns for reconstructions of parametric plasma expansion information from measured SAXS intensities. It is envisioned that the presented reconstruction framework can mature into a tool that is generally useful for the investigation of data attained by X-ray scattering techniques and can guide the development of models of the plasma dynamics towards the precise control of the properties of the produced ion beam and the upscaling of maximum attainable energies.

As a first and important step, the reconstructions need to be further developed to produce values of reconstructed parameters with error bars that are related to measurement errors. Further investigation of the comparison of the edge model intensity envelopes that compares the differences between the models to the measurement errors will reveal for which parameter ranges the presented models can be distinguished from one another. If they can be distinguished in reconstructions with measurement data, this would mean that more information about the expanded state of the plasma is attained than can be described by a single parameter and would effectively increase the resolution of the method.

Following studies should also include the investigation of the influence the choice of model quality measure has on the reconstructions' sensitivity to specific model parameters. The inclusion of adaptive masking and weighting factors is expected to enhance the results.

By the implementation of suitable density model class hierarchies analogical to the one presented in this work or even within a more general geometric framework, existing data from other experiment campaigns could also be made available to the framework.

An option that is especially interesting is the integration of the reconstruction framework with `simex_platform` [For+16] which is developed in the EUCALL project.

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A. DENSITY PACKAGE

File density_1d.py:

```
import numpy as np

class Abstract1d(object):
    """
    Abstract 1D function.
    """
    def __call__(self, x):
        return self.function(x)

class Abstract1dEdge(Abstract1d):
    """
    Abstract base class for edge models. Functor.
    """
    def __init__(self, slope_at_zero):
        """
        Initializer. Abstract, needs to be reimplemented by child classes.

        slope_at_zero: function slope at  $x=1$  that this functor object will
            ↪ have.
        """
        self.function = None
        raise NotImplementedError

    def __call__(self, x):
        """
        Return density at  $x$ .

         $x$ : spatial position at which the 1D density function is evaluated.
        """
        return self.function(x)
```

```

class AbstractFinite1d(Abstract1d):
    """
    Defined for a continuous finite interval only.
    """
    def __call__(self, x):
        self.range_check(x)
        return self.function(x)

    def range_check(self, x):
        if (x<self.lower_lim).any():
            raise ValueError
        if (self.upper_lim<=x).any():
            raise ValueError

class Symmetric1dFromEdge(Abstract1d):
    """
    Reflect at b/2.
    """
    def __init__(self, edge, offset):
        if not isinstance(type(edge), Abstract1dEdge):
            raise TypeError
        self.edge = edge
        self.offset = offset

    def function(self, x):
        return self.edge(x) * np.array(self._lower_part(x), dtype=float)+\
            self.edge(-x+self.offset) * np.array(self._upper_part(x), dtype
            ↪ =float)

    def _lower_part(self, x):
        return x<0.5*self.offset

    def _upper_part(self, x):
        return 0.5*self.offset<=x

class Finite1dSection(AbstractFinite1d):
    """
    Cut.
    """
    def __init__(self, f1d, lower, upper):
        if lower >= upper:
            raise ValueError
        self.lower_lim = lower

```

```

        self.upper_lim = upper
        self.function = f1d

class Periodic1dFromFinite(Abstract1d):
    """
    Align parts periodically.
    """
    def __init__(self, finite_feature):
        if not isinstance(type(finite_feature), AbstractFinite1d):
            raise TypeError
        self.finite_feature = finite_feature
        self.period_length = finite_feature.upper_lim - finite_feature.
            ↪ lower_lim
        self.function = lambda x : self.finite_feature(self.periodic_mapping(x
            ↪ ))

    def periodic_mapping(self, x):
        return (x-self.finite_feature.lower_lim)%self.period_length + self.
            ↪ finite_feature.lower_lim

```

File density_2d.py:

```

import density_1d

class Abstract2d(object):
    """
    Abstract 2D density function.
    """
    def __call__(self, x, y):
        return self.function(x, y)

class Wrap1dTo2d(Abstract2d):
    """
    Wraps a 1D function to a 2D function.
    """
    def __init__(self, wrap_1d, **kwargs):
        if not isinstance(type(wrap_1d), density_1d.Abstract1d):
            raise TypeError

        self.mapping_xy2x = kwargs.pop('mapping_xy2x', (lambda x,y : x))
        self.wrapped_1d = wrap_1d

    def function(self, x, y):
        t = self.mapping_xy2x(x, y)
        return self.wrapped_1d(t)

```

File `edge_functions_1d.py`:

```
import numpy as np
from scipy.special import erf
import density_1d

class SineEdge(density_1d.Abstract1dEdge):
    def __init__(self, param, **kwargs):
        mode = kwargs.pop('mode', 'slope')
        if mode == 'slope':
            self.slope_at_zero = param
            self.left = -np.pi/2/(2*self.slope_at_zero)
            self.right = np.pi/2/(2*self.slope_at_zero)

    def function(self, x):
        return self._f(x) * np.array(self._within(x), dtype=float) +\
            np.array(self._above(x), dtype=float)

    def _f(self, x):
        return 0.5*(1+np.sin(2.*self.slope_at_zero*x))

    def _below(self, x):
        return x<self.left

    def _within(self, x):
        return (self.left<=x) & (x<self.right)

    def _above(self, x):
        return self.right<=x

class StraightEdge(density_1d.Abstract1dEdge):
    def __init__(self, param, **kwargs):
        mode = kwargs.pop('mode', 'slope')
        if mode == 'slope':
            self.slope_at_zero = param
            self.left = -1./(2.*self.slope_at_zero)
            self.right = 1./(2.*self.slope_at_zero)

    def function(self, x):
        return self._f(x) * np.array(self._within(x), dtype=float) +\
            np.array(self._above(x), dtype=float)

    def _f(self, x):
        return 0.5*(1+2*self.slope_at_zero*x)
```

```

def _below(self, x):
    return self._f(x)<0

def _within(self, x):
    return (0<=self._f(x))&(self._f(x)<1)

def _above(self, x):
    return 1<=self._f(x)

class NormalEdge(density_1d.Abstract1dEdge):
    def __init__(self, param, **kwargs):
        mode = kwargs.pop('mode', 'slope')
        if mode == 'slope':
            self.slope_at_zero = param
        if mode == 'sigma':
            self.slope_at_zero = 1./(param * np.sqrt(2.*np.pi))

        self.left = -np.infty
        self.right = np.infty

    def function(self, x):
        return 0.5*(1+erf(x/(self.sigma()*np.sqrt(2))))

    def sigma(self):
        return 1./(self.slope_at_zero * np.sqrt(2.*np.pi))

class QuadEdge(density_1d.Abstract1dEdge):
    def __init__(self, param, **kwargs):
        mode = kwargs.pop('mode', 'slope')
        if mode == 'slope':
            self.slope_at_zero = param

        self.left = -1./self.slope_at_zero
        self.right = 1./self.slope_at_zero

    def function(self, x):
        return self._f(x) * np.array(self._within(x), dtype=float) +\
            np.array(self._above(x), dtype=float)

    def _f(self, x):
        return\
            (x<0.) * 0.5*self.slope_at_zero**2*(x-self.left)**2 +\
            (0.<=x) * (1.-0.5*self.slope_at_zero**2*(x+self.left)**2)

```

```

def _below(self, x):
    return x<self.left

def _within(self, x):
    return (self.left<=x) & (x<self.right)

def _above(self, x):
    return self.right<=x

class GaussEdge(density_1d.Abstract1dEdge):
    def __init__(self, param, **kwargs):
        mode = kwargs.pop('mode', 'slope')
        if mode == 'slope':
            self.slope_at_zero = param
            self.sigma = np.sqrt(2.*np.log(2))/(2.*self.slope_at_zero)
            self.mu = np.log(2.)/self.slope_at_zero

            self.left = -np.infty
            self.right = self.mu

    def function(self, x):
        return self._f(x) * np.array(self._within(x), dtype=float) +\
            np.array(self._above(x), dtype=float)

    def _f(self, x):
        return\
            np.exp(-(x-self.mu)**2/(2.*self.sigma**2))

    def _within(self, x):
        return x<self.right

    def _above(self, x):
        return self.right<=x

```

B. SIMULATION PACKAGE

File Models.py:

```
import numpy as np
import scipy.fftpack as fft
from scipy import signal
from density import density_1d
from density import edge_functions_1d
from density import density_2d

class BaseModel(object):
    """
    Base class for simulation items.
    """
    def __init__(self, **kwargs):
        save = kwargs.pop('save', None)
        self.save = save

    def __call__(self, params, interims, consts):
        self.calc(params, interims, consts)
        if self.save is not None:
            self.save()

    def calc(self, params, interims, consts):
        pass

class DistModelGrating2D(BaseModel):
    """
    Simulation item that wraps the density model.
    """
    def calc(self, params, interims, consts):
        edge = edge_functions_1d.NormalEdge(params['sigma'], mode='sigma')
        symm = density_1d.Symmetric1dFromEdge(edge, params['fsize'])
```

```

    feat = density_1d.Finite1dSection(symm, -0.5*(params['pitch']-params['
        ↪ fsize']), 0.5*(params['pitch']+params['fsize']))
    grat = density_1d.Periodic1dFromFinite(feat)
    grat2d = density_2d.Wrap1dTo2d(grat)
    dist = grat2d(consts['domain']['xx'], consts['domain']['yy'])
    interims['dist'] = dist

class CreateIllumination(BaseModel):
    """
    Simulation item that evaluates a the illumination function from
    ↪ reconstruction variable input.
    """
    def calc(self, params, interims, consts):
        xx = consts['domain']['xx']
        yy = consts['domain']['yy']
        ill = self._create_illumination(xx, yy, params['sill'])
        interims['illumination'] = ill

    def _create_illumination(self, xx, yy, sigma_ill):
        """
        Create circular square root of gaussian illumination function

        sigma_ill : sigma of gaussian, in number of pixels
        """
        shape = xx.shape
        small_y = (shape[0])//2
        large_y = shape[0] - small_y
        small_x = (shape[1])//2
        large_x = shape[1] - small_x
        pxidsy = np.arange(-small_y, large_y)
        pxidsx = np.arange(-small_x, large_x)
        pxidsxx, pxidsyy = np.meshgrid(pxidsx, pxidsy)
        g = np.exp(-0.5*((pxidsxx+1)**2 + (pxidsyy+1)**2)/sigma_ill**2)
        g = np.array(g/g.sum())
        g = np.sqrt(g)
        return g

class MultDistWithInterimIllumination(BaseModel):
    """
    Simulation item that imprints a variable illumination on the density.
    """
    def calc(self, params, interims, consts):
        illumination = interims['illumination']
        dist = interims['dist']
        dist = dist * illumination

```

```

interims['dist'] = dist

class MeasModelFarField2D(BaseModel):
    """
    Simulation item that evaluates the scattering model and the absolute
    ↪ square.
    """
    def calc(self, params, interims, consts):
        temp = fft.fft2(interims['dist'])
        temp = fft.fftshift(temp)
        interims['field_det'] = temp

class MeasModelFarFieldIntensity2D(BaseModel):
    """
    Measurement model: input (2D) -> 2D FFT -> absolute squared -> out
    """
    def calc(self, params, interims, consts):
        temp = fft.fft2(interims['dist'])
        temp = fft.fftshift(temp)
        meas = np.abs(temp)**2
        interims['meas'] = meas

def _convolve_with_psf(sharp_intensity, convolution_kernel):
    """
    Convolve the sharp intensity signal with the detector's PSF
    """
    out = signal.fftconvolve(sharp_intensity, convolution_kernel, mode='same'
        ↪ )
    return out

class ConvolveIntensityWithConstantPSF(BaseModel):
    """
    Simulation item that evaluates the effect of a constant detector PSF on
    ↪ the signal.
    """
    def calc(self, params, interims, consts):
        psf = consts['psf']
        meas = interims['meas']
        meas = _convolve_with_psf(meas, psf)
        interims['meas'] = meas

class ConvolveIntensityWithInterimPSF(BaseModel):

```

```

"""
Simulation item that evaluates the effect of a variable detector PSF on
    ↪ the signal.
"""
def calc(self, params, interims, psf):
    psf = interims['psf']
    meas = interims['meas']
    meas = _convolve_with_psf(meas, psf)
    interims['meas'] = meas

class AverageSquaredDifferences(BaseModel):
    """
    Simulation item that implements a measure of the intensity model quality.
    """
    def calc(self, params, interims, consts):
        mask = consts['mask'] if 'mask' in consts.keys() else None
        synth = interims['meas']
        meas = consts['meas']
        use_synth = synth*mask if mask is not None else synth
        use_meas = meas *mask if mask is not None else meas
        dim = np.sum(mask) if mask is not None else meas.size
        diff_sq = (use_meas - use_synth)**2
        q = np.sqrt(np.sum(diff_sq)*dim)
        interims['q'] = q

class MaximumSquaredDifferences(BaseModel):
    """
    Simulation item that implements a measure of the intensity model quality.
    """
    def calc(self, params, interims, consts):
        mask = consts['mask'] if 'mask' in consts.keys() else None
        synth = interims['meas']
        meas = consts['meas']
        use_synth = synth*mask if mask is not None else synth
        use_meas = meas *mask if mask is not None else meas
        diff_sq = (use_meas - use_synth)**2
        q = np.sqrt(np.max(diff_sq))
        interims['q'] = q

```

File Objective.py:

```

class Pipeline(object):
    """
    Functor to wrap simulation items in one object.
    """
    def __init__(self, steps):

```

```
self.steps = steps

def __call__(self, params, interims, consts):
    for step in self.steps:
        step(params, interims, consts)

class Objective(object):
    """
    Functor that returns the value of the intensity model quality measure.
    """
    def __init__(self, pl, consts, **kwargs):
        self.p_wrap = kwargs['p_wrap'] if 'p_wrap' in kwargs.keys() else None
        self.pl = pl
        self.consts = consts

    def __call__(self, p):
        interims = {}
        params = self.p_wrap(p)
        self.pl(params, interims, self.consts)
        return interims['q']
```

ERKLÄRUNG

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich diese Arbeit im Rahmen der Betreuung am Institut für Strahlenphysik des Helmholtz-Zentrums Dresden-Rossendorf ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter verfasst und alle Quellen als solche gekennzeichnet habe.

Malte Zacharias 9th November 2017